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D5.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA1

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D5.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA1

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
JRA	Joint Research Activity
AHA	Active and Healthy Ageing
RAI	Research Analysis Identifier
LL	Living Lab
RI	Research Infrastructure

Executive summary

Although Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be a “key” to the integration of research and innovation processes in real-life settings, they still fail to provide and function according to unified and harmonized processes that are easily accessible and exploitable by academic and industrial researchers. VITALISE brings together Living Labs across Europe (and 1 outside Europe in Canada) to create a Thematic ecosystem of Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain, aiming at creating synergies and transnational collaboration opportunities through innovative Joint Research Activities.

During VITALISE project three Joint Research Activities (JRAs) were implemented among the consortium Living Lab partners. These JRAs included state-of-the-art use cases that investigated AHA and chronic conditions in three important domains for the Health and Wellbeing Research. They were selected based on the consortium’s existing research studies and expertise: Rehabilitation, Transitional care and Everyday living environments (respectively JRA1, JRA2, JRA3).

The JRA of WP5 focused on the use of supportive technology for rehabilitation interventions and data collection in a rehabilitation context. We primarily aimed to gain insight in each living lab’s infrastructure and procedures in order to harmonise health and wellbeing living lab procedures and infrastructures in Europe and beyond, in particular in the context of rehabilitation. Secondly, we aimed to investigate the potential of innovative technologies for rehabilitation through living lab methodologies. Six small-scale pilot studies were preceded by co-creation sessions. This document presents an overview of the case studies performed in different countries.

1. Introduction

1.1 Description of the JRA process

The Joint Research Activities (JRAs) served as a test bed for all the internal harmonisation procedures, for assessing and improving the provided services, as well as the research cases that could be the basis for the external researchers through the transnational and virtual access procedures. Activities focused on three different domains in Living Lab Health & Wellbeing research: rehabilitation (WP5), transitional care (WP6) and everyday living environments (WP7).

In order to harmonise procedures as much as possible, **common JRA stand-up meetings** across WP5-6-7 were organised instead the bi-weekly WP5 meetings from 31/5/22 onwards. During these meetings we exchanged ideas, challenges and improvements for the activities that we performed in the JRAs and the procedures we agreed upon (such as a standard template for scenario, report and data collection methods, as well as recruitment strategy, etc.). After the first intensive phase, these meetings were organised monthly instead of bi-weekly. A Teams folder called *JRAs general channel* was created to share materials and reports. A **common template and scenario** were developed for data collection of the co-creation sessions of phase 1. Moreover, we decided to focus as much as possible on patients with stroke or mild cognitive impairments instead of including all chronic diseases.

To keep track of JRA progression, LiCalab created a **status report** Excel file called **Vitalise overview JRA activities** in which each partner regularly reported the status of his case study (preparation, deployment phase, running phase). The preparation phase showed the participants' sample size and profile as well as the status of ethical approval. In the deployment phase we determined how many participants were contacted, screened and recruited what the status of the information sessions was and, if applicable, whether technology was deployed. The running phase provided an overview of the data collection from pre, intermediary, and post measurements as well as data collection from devices, applications and software. Finally, the number of participants that completed the study was mentioned. Another tab in the file was meant to report discussions on challenges, actions required to resolve those, and lessons learned.

When the JRAs were finished, VILABS assessed the **socio-economic impact** of the JRA outcomes, gathering information from all Living Labs involved. This information is included at the end of the report.

1.2 Description of JRA1 - Rehabilitation supported by technology.

JRA1 (WP5) studied innovative solutions for rehabilitation in healthy participants, stroke patients and people with mild cognitive impairment (MCI). In Table 1, an overview is provided of all the engaged Living Labs of JRA1. An overview of the studies and the stakeholders involved in each study is presented in Table 2. In phase 1, multiple international living labs organised **co-creation sessions** with possible end-users to capture stakeholder perspectives on rehabilitation technology based on the principles of Design Thinking. During the co-creation sessions, the participants identified the problems causing low adherence in rehabilitation programs using technology and propose changes in the existing intervention tools. Usability and user acceptance were also assessed by clinicians, patients or healthy citizens. The scope was to identify any issues that may occur (e.g. feasibility, problems in technology deployment) in real life settings such as rehabilitation centres.

Data collection of the co-creation sessions (phase 1) started in August 2022 and ended June 2023. Furthermore, separate **small-scale pilots** were organised to test six innovative interventions or data collection technologies in practice using preliminary harmonised procedures (phase 2). A mixed-methods study design was adopted in which six (technological) interventions were implemented in rehabilitation practice across four countries (Greece, Spain, Belgium and Canada) in order to assess

user experience and usability of the innovation, and in some use cases explore the (preliminary) effects of the implemented intervention. The research protocol comprised a variety of study designs, including pre-post designs, controlled studies, or a collaborative participatory research design. Following that testing period, usability of each intervention was evaluated in relation to existing rehabilitation practices. Each Living Lab engaged end-users that experienced a rehabilitation intervention. Data collection of the small scale pilot studies (phase 2) started in February 2023 and finished in March 2024.

Table 1. Overview of the Living Labs and organisations involved in JRA1.

Abbreviation	Full (legal) name	Country
AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis	Greece
CRIR	Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation of Greater Montreal	Canada
GAIA	Association of Electronic and Information Technologies in the Basque Country	Spain
INTRAS	Fundación INTRAS	Spain
LiCalab	Living & Care Lab - Thomas More Kempen vzw	Belgium
McGill	McGill University	Canada
TREBAG	TREBAG Intellectual Property and Project Manager Ltd	Hungary
UDEM	Université de Montréal	Canada

1.3 Purpose of the document

This document describes the results of all JRA1-activities: the co-creation sessions of phase 1 as well as the small-scale studies of phase 2 that were performed across the five countries (Greece, Spain, Belgium, Canada and Hungary). Full protocols of the different case studies were presented in D5.1, and ethical approval preparations were displayed in D5.2.

1.4 Document Structure

During the joint meeting of 18/01/2024, participating partners (INTRAS, LAUREA, LICALAB, GAIA, AUTH) decided to restructure the presentation of the studies across all three JRAs for more clarity, based on an initial suggestion provided by UPM. All LL involved in the JRAs were invited to provide feedback on this proposal.

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1 Introduction** (this section) provides the description of the JRA process and JRA1 - Rehabilitation supported by technology, the purpose of the document as well as its structure.
- **Section 2 Case Studies Overview** consists of the JRA1 case studies across the five countries. First, the study is described, followed by the challenges encountered during execution. Next, outcomes and analyses are described. Finally, most important conclusions are shared.
- **Section 3. Harmonized Analysis across Living Labs.** This section comprises Living Lab harmonised services, JRA1 comparative results and challenges and the socio-economic impact assessment.
- **Section 4. Recommendations for Rehabilitation.** This section summarises the recommendations taken from all case studies.
- **Section 5. Conclusion** provides some concluding remarks for this deliverable.

2 Case Studies Overview

Table 2. Overview of co-creation sessions and small-scale pilot studies.

	AUTH <i>Short-arm centrifuge</i>	GAIA <i>Art therapy</i>	INTRAS <i>Gradior Cognitive</i>	LiCalab <i>Virtual mirror therapy</i>	UQAM - CRIR <i>Teledance</i>	McGill – UDEM - CRIR <i>Walkagain</i>	TREBAG <i>Co-creation</i>
Co-creation							
CP/Exp	11 - stroke	4 - experts	7 - rehabilitation	7 - stroke	NA	9 - stroke	5
Pts/C	NA	31 - healthy citizens	11 – MCI	NA	NA	NA	3 - patients
Small-scale pilot studies							
Aim	36 - stroke	20 - healthy	49 - MCI/early dementia 5 - clinicians	10-20 - stroke	15 - stroke 9 - clinicians	30 - stroke	NA
Status	8/18 intervention group 4/18 control group	9 - healthy	50 MCI/early dementia 5 clinicians	5 (4 hemiplegia, 1 arm/shoulder amputation)	5 stroke	4 stroke included, 1 completed	NA
IV	3 months 3x/week 1 hour per session	1 time demo 5 hours	4-6 months 2x/week 30 minutes	8 weeks 1x/week 1 time demo	5-6 weeks 6x/week 20 minutes	5 weeks 2x/week 1 hour	NA

Note. CP = Care professionals with area of expertise, Exp = (Technical) experts, Pts = Patients, C = Citizens, MCI = Mind cognitive impairment, IV = Intervention details. NA = Not applicable.

2.1 Case Study 1 - Short-Arm Human Centrifuge (AUTH/Greece)

2.1.1 Study description

Stroke is a medical condition that occurs when the blood supply to the brain is disrupted, either due to a blockage in the blood vessels (ischemic stroke) or bleeding into the brain tissue (haemorrhagic stroke). One of the most common and debilitating consequences of stroke is the impairment of movement. Different regions of the brain govern specific motor skills, and when a stroke occurs, the affected area determines the nature and extent of movement impairment. Commonly affected regions include the motor cortex, which is responsible for voluntary muscle control, and the cerebellum, involved in coordination and balance. The movement impairments resulting from stroke can significantly impact daily activities. Tasks that were once routine, such as walking, dressing, and eating, may become challenging or impossible. The loss of independence in mobility can have profound effects on an individual's quality of life, leading to increased dependency on others for assistance.

Advancements in stroke rehabilitation have provided hope for individuals seeking to regain lost function. Rehabilitation programs typically involve physical and occupational therapy, aiming to improve strength, coordination, and mobility. The intensity and duration of therapy vary based on the severity of the stroke and individual factors.

The short arm human centrifuge (SAHC) stands as an innovative infrastructure in aerospace technology, offering unique opportunities for research and training. Unlike traditional centrifuges, this compact yet powerful device focuses on simulating gravitational forces to understand their impact on the human body, particularly in scenarios like high-speed flight and space travel. Beyond its applications in aerospace research and pilot training, the SAHC is making significant strides in the field of medicine, as it is proving to be a versatile tool with diverse applications in medical research and therapy. The present study is exploring the contribution of the SAHC in minimizing the detrimental effects of immobility and lack of exercise. The effects on neuroplasticity for the improvement of executive functions are also investigated.

The SAHC infrastructure proposed in our research is a device created by our university's research group, as indicated by patent (#1009812/13/09/2019). It is located in the 'AUTH Human Centrifuge & Rehabilitation Living Lab'. Illustrated in Figure 1, this apparatus boasts a 4-meter diameter and can generate a gravitational load of +3.5 Gz at the feet. The system comprises a support base, motion mechanisms, and exercise systems like an adjustable-height bicycle and a horizontal rowing device. Additionally, two to four beds are attached to the central axis, rotating smoothly on wheels to improve user comfort. This structure is connected to an electric control panel located in the control room, ensuring safety and adherence to national and international regulations. Detailed information on the technical specifications of the SAHC can be found in the article written by Kourtidou-Papadeli et al. (2021). It has been validated for use with patients experiencing mobility disabilities. Moreover, the infrastructure can be equipped with electroencephalographic (EEG) devices for concurrent neurophysiological data collection, although our study treats them as distinct procedures in our outlined protocol (Kourtidou-Papadeli et al., 2022, Kourtidou-Papadeli et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Two-bed SAHC infrastructure. Having the patients lying in bed; the left patient has a bicycle ergometer, while the other patient has SAHC alone. Both are connected to a capturing data device.

The study consisted of two separate phases:

- The co-creation phase that aimed to identify the main challenges and opportunities when it comes to the use of the SAHC as a rehabilitation technique.
- The small-scale pilot study phase, following the research protocol and investigating the effectiveness of the SAHC as a rehabilitation technique in a cohort of stroke patients.

Co-creation session

The session took place during a dedicated workshop organized in the context of the SAN conference in September 2022. The agenda of the workshop is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Co-creation session time line

Duration	Activity	Team
10'	Welcome and registration	all
20'	Presentation of the infratsructure	all
50'	Presentation of the initial results	all
10'	Presentation of the Vitalise project	all
10'	Presentation of the research protocol	all

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20'	Q&A	all
30'	break	all
30'	demonstration	all
5'	Presentation of the questions	all
25'	Brainstorming ideas	participants
30'	discussion	all

The session attended healthcare professionals and other experts in the field of rehabilitation. The guiding questions used to navigate the session are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Research and guiding questions for the SAHC co-creation session

Research question	Guiding questions
What are the main challenges in using the centrifuge as a rehabilitation technique?	Based on what you saw here today, what would you think are the main challenges in using the centrifuge as a rehabilitation method from the healthcare professionals' perspective? Based on what you saw here today, what would you think are the main challenges in using the centrifuge as a rehabilitation method from the patients' perspective?
How can these challenges be resolved?	Looking at the identified challenges, can we try and find some potential solution for some of them?
What are the main opportunities in using the centrifuge as a rehabilitation technique?	Is there anything that you would like to be different or that could be improved? Can you identify the key points that would act as opportunities for using the human centrifuge as a rehabilitation technique?
How do they follow up on their patients?	What would move the healthcare professionals to incorporate the human centrifuge in their current rehabilitation methods? How can we attract patients to use the human centrifuge for rehabilitation?

To facilitate the discussion and assist in the presentation of the results, a canvas, markers and post-its were employed.

Small scale pilot study

The small-scale pilot aimed to evaluate the use of the SAHC for rehabilitation. To do that, the aim was to identify and onboard 36 participants (18 for the intervention and 18 for the passive control group). The number is not yet reached so the study will continue after the end of the VITALISE project to obtain high quality results of sufficient statistical power. The inclusion criteria are the following:

Inclusion criteria	
18-80 years old	Ability to provide informed consent
Not suffering from non-stabilised depression	Height <2m
No professional athletes	No history of chronic substance abuse (drugs, alcohol)
No recent surgeries	No heart arrhythmia
No major migraines	No pregnant women
No pregnant women	No epileptic patients
No kidney stones	No recent fractures
No acute inflammation	No recent stents or metallic plates and pins
No cognitive impairment	No history of syncope
No chronic pain, nausea, and vertigo	No psychiatric disorders

In order to evaluate the outcomes of the study, the following procedures were chosen, taken place 1-14 days prior to and after the intervention. The control group took part in the evaluation process twice, with a 3-month gap in between.

Neuropsychological evaluation

- Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE)
- Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA)
- Symbol-Digit Modalities Test (SDMT)
- Wechsler Memory Scale IV (WMS-IV)
- Neuropsychological Stroop test
- Verbal Fluency (X,S,A) (all)
- Hopkins Verbal Learning Test-Revised
- Trail making A+B
- Boston Naming Test
- Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9)
- Euro Quality of Life (EQ-5D-5L)
- Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI)
- State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) S and T

Physical Health evaluation

- 10m Walk Test
- Tinetti-test
- Berg Balance Scale (BBS)
- 6 Minute Walk Test (6MWT)
- Timed up and Go Test
- 3m backwards walk test
- Balance on one leg
- Handgrip Strength Test
- 30" Chair Stand Test

Neurophysiological evaluation

The evaluation was performed with a 128-channel EEG. It included:

- 5 minutes resting state paradigm with eyes open
- 5 minutes resting state paradigm with eyes closed
- Object naming
- Verb naming
- Sentence repetition

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- Finger tapping

General Health evaluation

- Weight and height measurement
- Arterial pressure, heart rate
- Spirometry
- Blood, urine, and saliva collection for the creation of the lipidemic profile and the realization of a full hormonal testing
- Hemodynamic measurements

The intervention lasted 3 months for each participant, 3 times per week, 1 hour per session. Each session included:

- Standing exercise
- 6 cycles, each consisting of 6 minutes of centrifugation followed by 5 minutes of rest. The gravitational levels varied between 0,7-2,5, and depended on the personal tolerance of each participant.

2.1.2 Execution and challenges

This small-scale pilot study focused on assessing the use of the SAHC as a rehabilitation technique for stroke patients. To participate in the study, the patients were initially contacted through their attending neurologist and given a brief explanation of the procedure and potential benefits. If they showed interest in it, an initial appointment at the iMedPhys premises was scheduled, where the patients were given more information, signed the informed consent form and participated in the EEG initial evaluation. Another appointment was then scheduled for the neuropsychological and physical evaluation. After the completion of these procedures, the patient visited the collaborating doctor and went through the general health evaluation as described above. Then, the intervention began with 3 weekly visits to the SAHC premises for 3 consecutive months, and once it was completed, the patients went over all the evaluations again.

The research protocol was complicated and required strong commitment on behalf of the participants. This posed specific challenges and barriers during the execution of the research. More specifically, the identified challenges are as follows:

- Skepticism on behalf of the medical professionals: Since the concept of SAHC is not particularly widespread and even less for medical reasons, most of the medical professionals contacted to assist with the patients' recruitment were not familiar with it. Although most of them were very keen on participating in such an endeavor, there were some that appeared skeptical and did not wish to contribute.
- Skepticism on behalf of the patients: The case of unwillingness due to the uniqueness of this technology was also encountered from the patients' side. Some patients or their relatives were unconvinced towards the safety of the infrastructure even though they were informed on the safety marks it holds.
- Compliance issues: The protocol was very strict, and the participants were encouraged to not miss more than one session subsequently. The infrastructure was located away from the town center, rendering it difficultly accessible.

2.1.3 Outcomes and Analysis

Co-creation session

Table 5. Level of technological literacy and previous contact with Vitalise for the clinicians involved in the SAHC co-creation session.

a/a	Age	Participants profile			Technology literacy				Previous contact with VITALISE project	
	Age range	Level of education	Field	Years of practice	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Excellent	YES	NO
1	25-30	MSc	Neuroscience	1						
2	25-30	MD	Medical Research	2						
3	30-35	MSc	Neuroscience	1						
4	25-30	MEng	Neuroscience	2						
5	25-30	MSc	Neuropsychiatry	4						
6	25-30	MSc, MD	Medical Research	1						
7	25-30	MSc	Neuropsychology	5						
8	25-30	MSc	Neuropsychology	2						
9	25-30	BSc	Neuropsychiatry	1						
10	30-35	PhD	Medical Research	9						
11	40-45	PhD	Research Health	15						

The session proved to be very fruitful, and the participants were highly engaged during the conversation. The main barriers identified when it comes to the use of the SAHC for rehabilitation were the distrust from the patients and the healthcare professionals due to their lack of knowledge on the matter, since the use of this technology for health promotion is a relatively new concept and up till now the main applications comprised space research. Proper dissemination of the results appeared to be the most prominent way to actually address these challenges. Many ethical and safety considerations were expressed by the participants but were all resolved during the session. Another obstacle was presented to be the cost of the built and maintenance of the SAHC and how this should be covered by the participants financial participation during the sessions. The use for

and economic support of the SAHC by research projects was suggested at least for the time being. The strict exclusion criteria for the use of the infrastructure were discussed, excluding many patients with chronic heart conditions etc. That obstacle cannot be bypassed, at least with the present technology. Among the most promising opportunities of the use of the SAHC for rehabilitation were identified to be the results that seem to appear even in the reorganization of the brain (the results presented were from previous studies in different populations), the simple rehabilitation protocol followed that doesn't require effort from the participants side and the variety of applications in space medicine already existing.

Figure 2. Pictures of the SAHC co-creation session with care professionals

Small scale pilot study

The study is currently underway, since the desired number of participants is not yet reached and in order to obtain high-quality results of sufficient statistical power. For this purpose, a preliminary analysis involving a small number of participants (12 patients, 8 in the intervention group) is presented here.

Evaluation and KPIs:

For the evaluation, the EEG picture naming paradigm and the resting state with eyes closed were selected. The rest of the outcome measures and paradigms will be analysed once the target number of participants has been reached.

1. Picture naming task: An image naming task (object naming task) comprised the first experimental phase. It lasted approximately 15 to 20 minutes with brief break intervals, the length of which was participant determined. The picture naming test had 131 inanimate (clothes, fruit, vegetables, cars, and household things) and 101 animate (animals and humans) images that were matched based on lexical factors including letter length, frequency, age of acquisition, and number of syllables, to name a few. PsychoPy software (Peirce JW, 2007) was used to carry out the picture naming activity, which was done in Greek. The participants' task was to observe objects on a computer display while sitting in an armchair in a soundproof room. With the monitor one meter from the participants' eyes,

each digital visual stimulus was automatically shown in the centre of the screen for two seconds.

The trials' arrangement was as follows: between two consecutive visual stimuli, a fixation cross (+) centred at the screen. To mitigate the effects of expectation and habituation, the fixation cross's display period was randomly adjusted between 300 and 750 ms. A 750-millisecond intertrial interval was utilized, and the image remained on the display for 2000 milliseconds or until a response was received. The task given to the participants was to identify each picture with a bare noun as fast as they could while paying close attention to how each stimulus was visually presented. Every subject received experimental trials at random. Using a voice key, response latencies between the start of the graphic stimulus and the start of the naming response were measured. The participants' vocal responses were documented throughout the experiment.

2. Resting state recording: During the second experimental phase, participants were instructed to sit in a chair with armrests, adopt a relaxed posture, and maintain stillness while keeping their eyes shut, while remaining awake for approximately 5 minutes.

Analysis methodology

Preprocessing pipeline was applied to 24 resting state EEG recordings and 16 ERP recordings. The pre-processing stage was conducted using the MATLAB environment (The MathWorks Inc. (2023), MATLAB version. R2023b) alongside custom-based scripts. Initially, triggers and DC channels were excluded from the raw EEG data. The remaining channels were then restructured with specific electrode positions for better spatial representation. The raw EEG data were subsequently re-referenced using a common average reference model to facilitate further analysis. Following that, digital filtering was conducted through a series of third-order Butterworth filters. This included high-pass filtering with a cutoff frequency at 0.3 Hz to eliminate linear trends, low-pass filtering with a cutoff frequency at 120 Hz to remove high-frequency noise, band-stop (notch) filtering to eliminate power interference signals (47–53 Hz), another band-stop filtering to eliminate the first-order harmonics of power interference (97–103 Hz), and finally, a band-stop filtering to eliminate the second-order harmonics of power interference (147–153 Hz). The bandwidth was selected based on our clinical preferences.

EEG data were then separated into signal and artefactual components using the Independent Component Analysis (ICA), performed through the EEGLAB graphical user interface (Delorme and Makeig, 2004). The signal decomposition resulted in 122 independent components that were further visually inspected in order to manually extract the remaining noise-contaminated components over time (pruning). Time epochs with biological artifacts were also excluded through visual inspection for the resting state EEG data.

EEG “bad” channels being unable to accurately or correctly record the electrophysiological signals of brain activity due to malfunctions like broken wire contact, electrodes that are improperly placed or poorly contacted with the scalp, were reconstructed using the mathematical tool of neighbour interpolation (NI), replacing the bad channel with the average of their first-neighbouring channels.

The further analysis was split into two primary parts. The first part involved functional connectivity analysis for resting state artifact-free EEG data, while the second involved an ERP analysis that was exclusively performed for the intervention group.

1. Cortical functional connectivity analysis: Functional network connectivity (FNC) analysis was conducted to identify the functional organization within and between resting networks. This analysis aimed to identify statistical dependencies between brain regions, which is referred to as functional connectivity. The analysis was conducted using the graphical user interface provided by Brainstorm (Tadel et al., 2011) and custom scripts in MATLAB. Sampling frequency was set as 1000 Hz and data were divided into nonoverlapping epochs with a

window of 8192 points. Epoch duration was 8,192 ms. Specified to the project, first the 122 electrodes were reordered and reached 130, creating a homogenous arrangement for the calculation of the inverse problem. The sLORETA technique was utilized to solve the inverse problem and estimate the brain activity (Pasqual-Marqui 2002), as implemented within the Brainstorm software, the known as ill-posed problem.

Solving the inverse problem: The M/EEG boundary element method was used within the Brainstorm to represent the generic head anatomy. Brainstorm's default parameters were used to model the cortex using 15,000 dipoles with a fixed orientation, going from the level of electrodes to level of cortical activations. The cortex is divided into the regions of interests (ROIs) and using the appropriate coordinates the activity of each region was estimated. The cortical activity for each region was assessed by determining the mean value of all the dipoles within that specific region. The procedure was implemented for 5 Regions of interest (ROIs) of the sensorimotor network, since it was deemed the most appropriate resting state network for use in stroke EEG analysis. Relative Wavelet Entropy (RWE) method is a tool used to calculate synchronization matrices representing the similarity in energy distribution between pairs of electrodes. RWE was used as a connectivity metric. The Network Based Statistics (NBS) Toolbox was employed to compute statistically significant differences through non-parametrical testing in the cortical activity among two different timepoints pre and post the intervention. The experiment consisted of resting state neurophysiological recordings performed on two distinct timepoints (1: preintervention, 2: post-intervention). Four participants were assigned to a control group and the remaining eight to the intervention group. **We are interested in identifying whether the intervention using the Short-Arm Human centrifuge with artificial gravity affected the participants (main effect of time) and proved to be beneficiary for post-stroke motor deficits.** Therefore, the main hypothesis was that functional connectivity would differ among the two time points (main effect of time) while expecting the participants in the intervention group would show better cortical functional connectivity in the post-intervention timepoint, when compared to the control group interaction. For the statistical F-test a repeated measures 2x2 ANOVA was utilized.

2. ERP Analysis: In this study, participants were exposed to 232 stimuli. Accuracy scores and response latencies were calculated for each participant at the pre and post levels by exploiting the recorded vocal responses. The EEG data were segmented based on stimulus onset and synchronized with the EEG recording. Unlike the resting state recordings where noisy time epochs were removed through visual inspection, all 232 epochs were retained due to the use of high-density EEG. However, ERPs were only extracted for accurate responses, and invalid responses were excluded. Each epoch consisted of 500 ms of the pre-stimulus interval and 2000 ms after the stimulus onset. First, the average response for all stimuli at the two time points was estimated. Per participant and timepoint (pre- and post-intervention), a two-dimensional ERP matrix was created. This matrix had 122 rows, representing the electrode positions, and 2500 points corresponding to the 2500 sample points constituting the ERP waveform. Given a sampling frequency of 1000 Hz, each sample point represented a duration of 1 ms. EEG analysis of this study focused on six areas of the brain, the anterior and posterior midline, left and right parietooccipital and the occipital areas across the two hemispheres. After averaging ERP matrices for all participants at pre and post intervention timepoints each 'grandaverage' waveform was computed. Grand averages were employed for visualizing distinct waveforms and determining the time window for the ERPs. However, the main analysis was executed on the individual two-dimensional ERP matrix of each participant.

All statistical analyses and visualizations were performed using R statistical software (R version 4.3.2 (2023-10-31)). Pair-sample t tests were used to compare the amplitude and latencies of the respective ERPs. However, on two cases, the Wilcoxon signed-rank exact test was employed due to the presence of outliers. Lastly, a repeated measures ANOVA was used solely to examine the effect of age and gender on behavioural data in the pre and post conditions.

Analysis:*Table 6. SAHC patient information*

participant	age	gender	handedness
1	67	female	right
2	74	female	right
3	60	female	right
4	60	male	right
5	64	male	right
6	68	female	right
7	58	female	right
8	60	male	right
9	71	male	left
10	78	female	right
11	73	male	right
12	70	male	right

Functional Connectivity analysis

The Network Based Statistics (NBS) analysis applied to the Sensorimotor Network revealed a statistically significant Time x Group Interaction effect ($p = 0.025$), suggesting distinctive alterations in functional connectivity between pre- and post-intervention timepoints. The design matrix, structured as a 2x2 repeated measures ANOVA, utilized a contrast vector [0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1], pointing the interaction term that distinguishes the post-intervention effects between the intervention and control groups. The number of edges (connections) identified as significant in the network were 6, indicating that there are six specific connections within the Sensorimotor Network where functional connectivity changes significantly across the two timepoints.

The number of nodes (regions of interest in the Sensorimotor Network) involved in these significant connections is 5, suggesting that alterations in functional connectivity are occurring across a subset of the five regions of interest. The significant Time x Group Interaction effect supports the main hypothesis. It suggests that the intervention using the Short-Arm Human Centrifuge with artificial gravity has had an impact on the functional connectivity of participants in the intervention group compared to the control group.

D5.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA1

Figure 3. NBS resulted in a Functional network with five nodes and six sub-connections (LPGLMC, SMA-LMC, SMA-RMC, LMC-RMC, RMC-RPG, LPG-RPG). Visualisation from three different views of the brain are presented: sagittal, coronal, and axial.

ERP analysis

Object naming. After removing outliers like incorrect naming responses and latencies, mean accuracy scores and response latencies were extracted for the eight stroke subjects who participated in the intervention at two separate time points (pre and post intervention). Results are presented in the table below.

Table 7. Pre vs. post intervention mean accuracy and response latency during the object naming task

	Accuracy (%)	Response Latency (sec)	Imageability (1-7 scale)
PRE	75.16% (0.26)	1.12 (0.13)	2.448(0.019)
POST	69.75% (0.12)	1.13 (0.15)	2.452(0.017)

In the examination of naming accuracy within the context of a paired-sample t-test applied to pre and post-intervention conditions, no statistically significant difference emerged. This analysis sought to investigate potential alterations in the subjects' performance during naming tasks based on behavioural data. The absence of statistical significance in the paired-samples t-test suggests a

consistency in naming accuracy and response latency reinforcing the notion of sustained performance across the pre- and post-intervention states.

Utilizing a repeated measures ANOVA, changes in naming accuracy and latency before and after intervention were assessed, considering potential interactions with gender and age.

The outcomes of the repeated measures ANOVA examining the impact of intervention and gender on naming accuracy revealed that neither the main effect of Timepoint (pre and post-intervention) ($F(1, 10) = 0.023$, $p = 0.883$) nor the interaction effect between Timepoint and Gender ($F(1, 10) = 0.784$, $p = 0.397$) was statistically significant, indicating that the change in naming accuracy over time does not significantly differ between genders. Collectively, these findings suggest that any observed variations in naming accuracy are attributed to random variability rather than systematic effects associated with the intervention or gender.

The repeated measures ANOVA examining the impact of timepoint and gender on response latencies in stroke patients revealed non-significant effects. The interaction between timepoint and gender ($F = 0.156$, $p = 0.701$) was not statistically significant. Most of the variability in response latencies was observed within subjects rather than between different timepoints or genders.

We also used linear regression to explore whether age affects naming accuracy and latency in stroke patients. The model estimates coefficients for the intercept and age, aiming to understand whether a linear association exists between age and naming accuracy. In exploring whether age influences naming accuracy in stroke patients, the analysis did not show a significant relationship. The p-value of 0.875 suggests that age does not have a meaningful impact on how well individuals in this study named objects. The tiny coefficient (0.001337) reinforces this, indicating a minimal change in naming accuracy for each additional year of age. The overall model, including age, did not explain much of the variation in naming accuracy (R-squared of 0.001834).

The linear regression analysis exploring the relationship between age and response latencies in stroke patients yielded non-significant results ($p = 0.48$). The coefficient for age was -0.003080, suggesting a minimal decrease in response latency with increasing age, though this effect was not statistically significant. The model did not provide a meaningful explanation for the variability in response latencies, as indicated by the low multiple R-squared (0.03626) and adjusted R-squared (-0.03258) values. In summary, age does not appear to be a significant predictor of response latencies in this study.

Imageability, or imagery, measures how well a word or stimuli prompts a mental image or sensory experience (Rofes et al., 2018). Imageability measurements may be useful for cognitive rehabilitation outcomes. In the context of this experiment, after removing all invalid responses, we calculated the mean imageability score for the pictures identified correctly for each participant in the pre and post condition. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test was conducted to assess whether there was a significant difference in imageability scores between the pre- and post-intervention conditions. The test yielded a p-value of 0.05747, which is close to, but slightly above, the conventional significance level of 0.05. While the result is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level, it suggests a trend towards a potential difference in imageability scores following the intervention.

D5.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA1

Figure 4. Imageability scores per participants and per condition

The visual trend observed in the data, showing higher values for each participant in the postintervention condition, aligns with the numerical result of the test. While the p-value did not reach conventional significance, the trend among participants suggests a positive inclination towards improved performance with stimuli of higher imageability.

Event Related Potentials: Grand-average ERPs amplitudes for eight stroke patients in Pre and post intervention timepoints. ERPs were elicited for six distinct brain regions. Blue and red lines represent the intervention group's ERP valid responses during the Pre and Post intervention conditions.

Figure 5. Average ERPs plots for the Parietooccipital areas. In the left parietooccipital area, the P100 peak exhibits a notable increase post-intervention compared to pre-intervention. Noteworthy differences also observed also for the Slow Positive Wave (SPW) in the right parietooccipital area. Statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) was only identified for the P100 component. The stimuli was given at 500 ms.

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Figure 6. The anterior midline of the brain typically includes structures such as the frontal lobes, while the posterior midline represents regions like the occipital lobes. N100 amplitude is increased in the post condition, while in the posterior midline SPW shows a significant increase around 1500 ms post stimulus.

Figure 7. In the occipital areas ERP components P200 and the Slow Positive amplitudes are increased post intervention. P200 component in the right occipital region increases statistically significant.

Analysing the impact of the intervention on ERP N100 amplitudes at the anterior midline, we conducted a paired samples t-test on data from eight participants, comparing pre- and postintervention values. The obtained results, including a t-statistic of -0.72178 with 6 degrees of freedom, yielded a p-value of 0.4976. In simpler terms, the test aimed to determine if there was a significant difference in N100 amplitudes after the intervention. However, the outcomes showed that the observed difference was not statistically significant at the commonly used 0.05 significance level. The 95 percent confidence interval ranged from -1.241768 to 0.676054, indicating that the true mean difference could be zero, suggesting no substantial change in N100 amplitudes. Therefore, based on the paired t-test, we did not find enough evidence to reject the idea that the intervention had a significant impact on ERP N100 amplitudes at the anterior midline. Also, a paired samples t-test was conducted on the latencies obtained from eight participants, with pre-latencies ranging from 72ms to 123ms and post-latencies from 76ms to 126ms. Comparing pre and post values at the anterior midline, revealed no statistically significant differences either for latencies.

On the posterior midline area, in terms of neurophysiological recordings referring to electrodes that are strategically positioned to record electrical activity primarily from the parietal and occipital lobes of the brain the analysis of the Slow Positive Wave (SPW) amplitude, using The Wilcoxon signed rank exact test indicated a statistically significant p-value of 0.039060, which is below the conventional significance level of 0.05 with a test statistic (V) of 3. In the context of this test, V represents the smaller of the two sums of ranks calculated for the positive and negative differences between paired observations. A smaller V value suggests that the sum of ranks for the set of differences (either positive or negative) with the smaller sum is 3. This outcome indicates a

D5.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA1

substantial likelihood that the observed differences are not purely the result of random chance. Consequently, we reject the null hypothesis, which posits no difference, and infer that the intervention has induced a statistically significant shift in the amplitude measurements.

Figure 8. Distributions of the Slow Positive Wave amplitudes and latencies extracted on Pre and Post level.

While the statistical test for latencies did not yield any significance, observations on the data suggest a potential increase in latencies post-intervention, indicating slower waves. The small sample size may have influenced the statistical outcome.

Figure 9. P100 component amplitudes and latencies change in pre and post conditions.

On the left parietooccipital area, the analysis of the P100 amplitudes indicated a significant time effect. A paired sample t-test was employed which revealed a significant difference in amplitude means ($t = 3.0276$, $p = 0.01264$), suggesting a notable shift in neurophysiological responses following the intervention. The degrees of freedom are approximately 10.064. The calculated 95% confidence interval [0.4560309, 2.9896834] further supports this finding, with a range that does not include zero, emphasizing the robustness of the observed amplitude change and supports the rejection of the null hypothesis.

The paired sample t-test conducted on latency data for P100 component, comparing pre- and postintervention measurements, did not reveal a statistically significant difference ($t = 1.1011$, $p = 0.3073$). The calculated 95% confidence interval for the mean difference spans from -10.75874 to 29.50874, encapsulating zero. This outcome suggests that, at the current sample size, there is insufficient evidence to support a definitive change in latencies following the intervention. The observed mean difference of 9.375 highlights a variability within the data.

In the context of neurophysiological measures, P100 latency typically represents the time taken for the brain to process specific stimuli. A reduction in P100 latency could imply an enhancement in the speed of neural processing, which may be interpreted positively in certain contexts.

Figure 10. Distribution of the P200 amplitudes and latencies for each participant in pre and post conditions.

In the analysis of paired amplitude data, a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was performed to assess the impact of the intervention on the right occipital area. The test yielded a p-value of 0.03125, surpassing the significance threshold of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis, suggesting no difference in amplitude distributions between pre- and post-intervention, was rejected. This indicates a statistically significant shift in amplitudes, affirming the intervention's effect on the right occipital area. To visually represent this finding, a plot illustrating the distribution of pre- and postintervention amplitudes can be generated.

A second paired t-test conducted on P200 latencies indicated a p-value of 0.3709, suggesting that there is not a statistically significant difference between the mean latencies before and after the intervention. The non-significant result could be influenced as well by the limited sample size, but observation on the data, suggest a potential slight decreasing tendency in latencies after the intervention.

2.1.4 Conclusions

The main aim of the present study was to assess the use of the SAHC for rehabilitation purposes. The analysis did not manage to provide conclusive evidence that the intervention improved stroke survivors quality of life but offers early indications of enhanced neuroplasticity and a broad activation of the brain. These controversial findings and the limited sample size prevent us from drawing definite conclusions about the impact of the intervention, but they add to the increasing body of evidence supporting the potential of SAHC as a tool for neurorehabilitation. As a result, we decided to continue with the recruitment until a large number of participants (up to a total of 36 (50-50 intervention-control group) is reached and the results have a great statistical significance. Overall, SAHC appears to be positively viewed by experts and the initial results seem to support the hypothesis for brain pathway reorganization.

2.2 Case Study 2 - Art therapy (GAIA/Spain)

2.2.1 Study description

Art Therapy and Stress Relief

Stress is a widespread and debilitating condition that affects the quality of life of many people. It can cause physical, psychological, and emotional problems, and interfere with personal and professional goals. Art therapy is a form of expressive therapy that uses the creative process of making art to improve well-being and cope with stress. Podcasts are a popular and accessible medium that can deliver art therapy and rehabilitation interventions to a large and diverse audience. However, there is a lack of research on the effectiveness and feasibility of podcasts as a delivery method for art therapy.

The aim of this study is to examine the effects of art therapy on stress relief in adults. The study has four main phases: preparation, deployment, running, and assessment. The first part of the case study was focus on the development of podcasts in music, literature, dance and cinema. In the preparation phase, the researchers conducted a literature review, obtained ethical and legal approval, and designed the podcast episodes with the collaboration of different stakeholders identified for the co-creation session. In the deployment phase, the researchers recruited participants, assigned them to experimental or control groups, and provided them with the necessary equipment and instructions. In the running phase, the participants listened to the podcast episodes in different sessions and participated in an art therapy pilot (painting). In the assessment phase, the researchers collected and analysed data from pre-test and post-test questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups.

The study also involved a co-creation process, in which the researchers collaborated with potential users and stakeholders to design and evaluate the podcast episodes. The co-creation process consisted of two sessions, in which the participants provided feedback and suggestions on the content, format, and delivery of the podcasts. The researchers also conducted a small-scale pilot study, in which they tested the feasibility and acceptability of the podcasts and other art therapy with a sample of participants.

The main research questions of the study are:

- What is the impact of podcasts of art therapy on stress relief in adults?
- How do the participants perceive and experience the podcasts of art therapy?
- What are the strengths and limitations of podcasts as a delivery method for art therapy?
- How can the podcasts of art therapy be improved and refined based on the co-creation and pilot feedback?

Data collection phase 1: Co-creation

For the co-creation sessions the followed steps during this process were the identification of stakeholders participating in the activity, identification of places for co-creation session, and the development of the content of podcasts.

Stakeholder identification: Participants from the following institutions or areas:

- Gernika Kultur Etxea
- Mondragón University
- Gernika citizens
- GAIA
- Press media

Number of participants 31 in different sessions,

Activities performed:

- Design and structuring Smart Spaces for co-creation sessions with stakeholders
- Recording (Audio and video) + edition of podcast of Literature, Music, Dance and Cinema with stakeholders.
- Creation of content in different digital platforms such as Youtube, SoundCloud and Spotify together with stakeholders

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GjyM5V9lbbk>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8sm8eRXDUug>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=12RcZkeLzjw>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lq938yvNpfc>

Figure 11. Cocreation of four Podcasts related to performing arts as tools for stress avoidance with stakeholders.

Data collection phase 2: Small scale pilot study

This small-scale pilot was conducted by GAIA & The University of Vlora. Art therapy through painting for older adults is a form of expressive therapy that leverages the creative process of making art to improve and enhance the physical, mental, and emotional well-being of aging adults. This therapeutic approach recognizes the unique challenges and opportunities that come with older age.

Number of participants: 9 (older adults from 75 years to 94 years)

Researchers: 5

Procedure:

- Pre- session survey to identify the initial situation of the participants in the piloting session (different assessment used: Edmonton Symptom Assessment System, Functional Assessment of Chronic Illness Therapy, Spiritual Well-being-Spiritual FACIT,)

D5.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA1

- Painting session. Using a template (picture projected in the screen), participants had to represent the painting using their interpretation, colours, etc.
- Post-session survey. Collecting the feeling of participants after the session (FEATS scale, personnel impression)
- Using IA generative interpretation of the feeling's and emotions of participants in the session.

Figure 12. Small scale pilot - Art therapy session: Painting session.

Using IA for the emotional analysis, the researchers analysed the paintings considering the colours and the interpretation of the objectives included in the paintings. For this analysis the Chatgtp4 tool was used.

Type of the analysis performed:

The choice of bright, opposing colours and the central image of a tree with a heart-shaped leaf suggests a state of hopeful resilience. The painter appears to channel an energetic optimism, confronting a challenge yet finding a space for growth and positivity amidst them. The aggressive brushwork indicates a passionate engagement with the painting process, hinting at a dynamic and spirited emotional state.

Figure 13. Energetic optimism: an example of a painting created during the small scale pilot study.

2.2.2 Execution and Challenges

In the study of art therapy focusing on the participation of older adults in a painting therapy pilot, significant progress has been made in understanding the potential benefits and challenges associated with this therapeutic approach. The study has demonstrated that art therapy, specifically through painting, can offer numerous psychological and emotional benefits for elderly participants. These benefits include improved mood, enhanced cognitive function, and increased social interaction, which are crucial for the well-being of older individuals.

However, the study also encountered several significant barriers and challenges. One of the primary challenges was the varying levels of physical ability among participants, which affected their ability to engage in painting activities. Some participants faced difficulties with fine motor skills or vision impairments, which required adjustments to the therapy sessions to accommodate their needs. Another challenge was the initial resistance from some participants who were sceptical about the effectiveness of art therapy or who felt they lacked artistic talent. Overcoming this barrier involved creating a supportive and non-judgmental environment that encouraged participation and emphasized the process over the final product.

Furthermore, logistical issues such as securing appropriate and accessible venues for the therapy sessions, along with ensuring the availability of materials, posed additional challenges. Ensuring the sessions were adequately staffed to provide individual attention and support to participants was also a critical factor in the success of the pilot.

Despite these challenges, the pilot study has laid a foundation for further research into the benefits of art therapy for older individuals. It has highlighted the importance of adapting art therapy practices to meet the diverse needs of older participants and has underscored the potential of painting therapy as a valuable tool for enhancing the quality of life for the older adult population.

Adding to the initial summary, here are some key barriers encountered during the art therapy pilot study with older participants:

- **Accessibility Issues:** Ensuring that the therapy sessions were accessible to all participants, including those with mobility issues or those who required transportation assistance to attend the sessions.
- **Cultural and Personal Beliefs:** Overcoming cultural and personal beliefs that may devalue or misunderstand the purpose and benefits of art therapy, which could deter participation or full engagement from some older individuals.
- **Technological Barriers:** For any components of the program that relied on technology, such as online sessions (podcasts), some participants faced challenges due to limited technological literacy or access to necessary devices and internet services.

- **Financial Constraints:** Budget limitations for the program could affect the quality and quantity of materials available, as well as the ability to hire experienced art therapists, potentially impacting the overall effectiveness of the therapy. Participants indicated that this kind of art session can be expensive if they are not supported by a governmental institution or association. Considering that older people are pensioners the access to this type of therapy may be restricted due to a limited budget.
- **Health and Safety Concerns:** Managing health and safety concerns, especially important in working with an older population that may have various health conditions, require modifications to the program to ensure a safe environment for all participants.
- **Emotional and Psychological Barriers:** Addressing emotional and psychological barriers, such as fear of failure, anxiety about trying new activities, or past traumas that might surface during the creative process, required sensitive handling by skilled therapists.
- **Interpersonal Dynamics:** Navigating the interpersonal dynamics within the group, including conflicts or competitiveness, which could affect the collaborative and supportive atmosphere intended in art therapy sessions.

These barriers highlight the complexity of implementing an art therapy pilot program for older participants and underscore the need for careful planning, flexibility, and sensitivity to the diverse needs and concerns of this population.

The living lab services used during the co-creation and piloting phase focused on expert opinion, advisory services, stakeholder analysis and mapping, validation test, idea selection and testing.

2.2.3 Outcomes and Analysis

Evaluating the effectiveness of an art therapy program, especially one designed for older participants, involves a comprehensive methodology that encompasses both qualitative and quantitative measures. The goal is to capture the holistic impact of the program on participants' well-being, social interaction, cognitive function, and emotional health. Here's an outline of the evaluation methodology and key performance indicators (KPIs) that were considered:

Evaluation Methodology:

1. **Pre- and Post-Program Assessments:** Conduct assessments of participants' mental, emotional, and physical well-being before the program starts and after it concludes. These assessments can include standardized psychological tests, physical health evaluations, and cognitive function tests.
2. **Ongoing Observations:** Throughout the program, facilitators and therapists should make regular observations regarding participants' engagement, behaviour changes, and interaction with peers. This qualitative data is invaluable for understanding the program's impact on a day-to-day basis.
3. **Participant Feedback:** Collect feedback from participants through interviews, focus groups, or surveys. Questions should cover their experiences, perceived benefits, challenges faced, and suggestions for improvement.
4. **Family and Caregiver Feedback:** Since family members and caregivers can provide insights into changes in the participants' behaviours and moods outside of the therapy sessions, their feedback is crucial.
5. **Staff and Volunteer Feedback:** Gather insights from those who conducted the sessions to learn about operational challenges, participant responses, and the overall effectiveness of the program structure and content.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):

1. **Engagement Levels:** Measure the participation rate, session attendance, and active involvement in activities to assess engagement.

2. **Mood and Emotional Well-being Improvement:** Use standardized scales (e.g., the Geriatric Depression Scale) pre- and post-program to evaluate changes in mood and emotional health.
3. **Cognitive Function Changes:** Assess any changes in cognitive function using appropriate tools (e.g., Mini-Mental State Examination) to determine if the art therapy has had a cognitive impact.
4. **Social Interaction and Connectivity:** Track changes in social behaviours, such as increased interactions with peers, more frequent participation in group discussions, or expressions of empathy and support among participants.
5. **Participant Satisfaction:** Measure participant satisfaction with the program's content, facilitators, and overall experience.
6. **Artistic Expression Growth:** Although more qualitative, evaluating the evolution of participants' artistic expressions over time can provide insights into their emotional and cognitive engagement with the therapy.
7. **Physical Health Indicators:** Monitor any reported changes in physical health or mobility, which can be influenced by overall well-being and engagement in activities.
8. **Program Attrition Rates:** Keep track of dropout rates to identify potential issues with program design or execution that may need to be addressed.

By integrating these evaluation methodologies and KPIs, program administrators and therapists can gain a comprehensive understanding of the art therapy program's effectiveness, areas for improvement, and the overall impact on the elderly participants' quality of life.

Outcomes:

- Awarded as the best community engagement project in the Basque Country
- 4 podcasts: Literature, music, dance and cinema
- Emotional analysis of piloting results
- Pre- test and post- test analysis

2.2.4 Conclusions

The development of an art therapy pilot program with painting for elderly participants offers valuable insights and lessons learned that can guide future initiatives. Here is a **list of key lessons learned**:

1. **Flexibility is Key:** Tailoring sessions to accommodate the varied physical and cognitive abilities of participants ensures that everyone can engage meaningfully with the activities.
2. **Creating a Safe Space:** Establishing a non-judgmental and supportive environment encourages participants to express themselves freely and benefits their emotional well-being.
3. **Importance of Social Interaction:** Facilitating opportunities for social interaction within the sessions can significantly enhance the therapeutic experience, combatting loneliness and fostering a sense of community among participants.
4. **Adaptability of Materials and Methods:** Adapting materials and methods to meet the needs and preferences of elderly participants, such as using larger brushes or offering magnifying tools, can greatly improve accessibility and enjoyment.
5. **Cultural Sensitivity:** Being mindful of the cultural backgrounds and personal histories of participants enriches the therapy process and ensures that it is respectful and relevant.
6. **Professional Guidance is Crucial:** Having skilled art therapists who are trained in working with older populations ensures that the sessions are therapeutic and cater to the specific needs of the participants.
7. **Feedback Mechanisms:** Implementing regular feedback mechanisms helps in adjusting the program to better meet the needs of the participants and in identifying areas for improvement.
8. **Highlighting the Process Over Product:** Emphasizing the creative process rather than the final artwork helps participants focus on the experience of creation, which is where the therapeutic value lies.

9. **Awareness of Emotional Triggers:** Being prepared to address emotional responses or memories that the art-making process may evoke is important for providing the necessary support and guidance.
10. **Integration with Other Therapies:** Combining art therapy with other therapeutic approaches can enhance the overall well-being of the participants, offering a more holistic approach to care.
11. **Documenting Progress and Outcomes:** Keeping detailed records of sessions, including participants' progress and responses, can provide valuable insights for refining the program and demonstrating its benefits.

These lessons learned highlight the importance of a thoughtful and individualized approach to implementing art therapy with painting for older individuals, emphasizing the need for professional expertise, adaptability, and a focus on creating a supportive and enriching environment.

Building on the lessons learned from the art therapy pilot program with painting for older adult participants, here are several recommendations to enhance the effectiveness and impact of future programs:

1. **Ensure Accessibility:** Make sure the venue is easily accessible to those with mobility issues and consider providing transportation for those who may need it.
2. **Train Staff and Volunteers:** Invest in training for staff and volunteers on the nuances of working with older populations, including understanding common physical and cognitive challenges.
3. **Incorporate a Range of Activities:** Include a variety of painting and art-making activities to cater to different interests and abilities, keeping sessions engaging and inclusive.
4. **Foster Interpersonal Connections:** Create structured opportunities for participants to share their work and experiences with the group, fostering a sense of community and mutual support.
5. **Provide Individualized Support:** Offer personalized guidance and support during sessions, acknowledging that each participant has unique needs and preferences.
6. **Utilize Adaptive Tools:** Equip the program with adaptive tools and materials that accommodate limitations in dexterity, vision, or other physical challenges faced by older adults.
7. **Engage with Families and Caregivers:** Involve participants' families and caregivers in the process, providing them with updates and inviting them to participate in certain sessions or events.
8. **Monitor and Address Mental Health:** Be vigilant about the mental health of participants, offering referrals to additional support services if needed and ensuring that art therapy sessions are conducted in a way that is mindful of potential emotional vulnerabilities.
9. **Regularly Evaluate and Adapt the Program:** Continuously assess the effectiveness of the program through feedback from participants, staff, and volunteers, making necessary adjustments to improve the experience.
10. **Promote the Benefits of Art Therapy:** Actively communicate the benefits of art therapy to potential participants, their families, and the broader community to encourage participation and support for the program.
11. **Leverage Technology Wisely:** Consider incorporating technology that can enhance the art-making process or facilitate social connections, while being mindful of the technology's accessibility and ease of use for elderly participants.
12. **Build Partnerships:** Collaborate with local community centres, healthcare facilities, and educational institutions to expand the reach and resources of the art therapy program.

Implementing these recommendations can significantly enhance the quality and impact of art therapy programs for elderly participants, ensuring that they are accessible, enjoyable, and therapeutically beneficial.

2.3 Case Study 3 - Gradior Cognitive (INTRAS rehabilitation Living Lab/ Spain)

2.3.1 Study description

Objective

This study aimed to assess the latest Gradior Cognitive functionalities, focusing on their usability and preliminary effectiveness for therapists and older adults. It explored user experience, satisfaction, and therapist perspectives on the system's new features designed for cognitive training in individuals at risk or with deficits. This evaluation is part of a continuous effort to enhance digital tools, incorporating the latest version's advancements in patient management and follow-up capabilities.

Technological resources used:

Gradior Cognitive: Neuropsychological evaluation and rehabilitation system for carrying out training programmes in people with deficits and/or cognitive impairment. It allows working in adults Attention, Perception, Orientation, Memory, Calculation, Executive Function, Language and Reasoning. The system consists of a website (aimed at professionals) and an app for the execution of intervention sessions by users.

The set of data collected in Gradior consists of the accumulated results of the sessions executed taking into account the data between the first session executed and the last session executed, the values collected correspond to the % of global successes and by cognitive areas (attention, calculation, executive function, language, memory, orientation, perception and reasoning). A single record is obtained for each patient, which is edited as the sessions are carried out. Collects information on performance in the exercises provided by the tool: total time per test, assigned treatment (cognitive areas, modalities, and levels), gradior score through a weighted value or cognitive evolution index by cognitive area based on the level of difficulty, reaction times.

Collects also as static data profile data fields and a brief clinical history, e.g., some sociodemographic information, relevant background, medication that may influence cognitive performance; results from validated scales of interest (Geriatric Depression Scale; Mini-Mental State Examination, etc.).

Minimum requirements: Intel Core i3 (6th generation or higher), Memory: RAM 4GB minimum and Operating System: Windows 10 Fall Creators Update OS Build 16299.

Development:

To attain our overall objective, the study included:

- Firstly, co-creation sessions were orchestrated, with a dual focus: a comprehensive examination of technology's role in rehabilitation and, more specifically, an in-depth exploration of the feelings (elicited by the program), perspectives, opinions, and expectations of participants regarding the novel functionalities of Gradior Cognitive.
- Secondly, a pilot activity was executed, engaging end users alongside social and health professionals. This pilot endeavor was designed to provide a practical testbed for the integration and evaluation of the new functionalities of Gradior Cognitive.

Data collection phase 1: Co-creation sessions

The primary objectives of the co-creation sessions covered, firstly, addressing the issue of technologies within the rehabilitation process from a comprehensive perspective shared across all living labs. Simultaneously, these sessions aimed to explore the feelings and expected utility of the

Gradior Cognitive program. This exploration was performed in group sessions where users were provided with opportunities to articulate their opinions, sensations (pertaining to what the program conveys to them), perspectives, viewpoints, and expectations.

The co-creation sessions took place in October 2022 at the INTRAS Foundation's Parquesol centre in Valladolid. These sessions saw active participation from a carefully selected group of 11 end users who met specific inclusion and exclusion criteria, alongside 7 therapists from INTRAS clinics. Participants were over 55, voluntarily involved, and capable of informed consent, with mild cognitive impairment or early-stage dementia indicated by MMSE scores between ≥ 21 and ≤ 27 . They exhibited memory or thinking issues more significant than typical aging effects, without major impacts on daily activities. Excluded were those with severe sensory impairments, inability to consent, psychiatric or neurological conditions that limit participation, substance abuse, or those on antipsychotic medication.

Each session, with a maximum duration of 2 hours, was conducted separately for each participant profile (end users and professionals). This separation was designed to tailor the materials utilized, and both sessions adhered to a standardized structure: a conducive environment was created for a roundtable discussion accompanied by a presentation. The presentation outlined the focal topic of discussion, and structured open questions were grouped thematically to guide the collaborative exploration.

Table 8. Co-creation scenario

PART 1	
<p>FOR ALL USERS (PROFESSIONALS AND CLIENTS/OLDER ADULTS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exploring the Impact of Technology in Rehabilitation: Could you share your perception about the benefits and challenges associated with incorporating technology into rehabilitation processes? ▪ User Reception and Acceptance: To what extent is the technology accepted by the (social and healthcare) users? (both professionals and clients/older adults) <p>FOR PROFESSIONALS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rehabilitation Journey Mapping: Can you outline how the rehabilitation pathway is structured across various settings such as hospitals, rehabilitation centres, and private practices? ▪ Funding and Reimbursement Insights: Are patients typically reimbursed for rehabilitation sessions? Is there a reimbursement policy for e-health applications in the rehabilitation sector? ▪ Best Practices and Preferences: What are recognized best practices in leveraging technology for rehabilitation? Between physical and remote sessions, which do you prefer, and why? 	
PART 2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Does the solution fit the needs of the person(s)? ▪ How useful do you expect the new functionalities of Gradior Cognitive to be? ▪ How will you complement the approach with Gradior Cognitive? ▪ What is the ideal usage scenario for you? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Does the solution fit the needs of the person(s)? ▪ How useful do you expect the new functionalities of Gradior Cognitive to be? ▪ How will you complement the approach with Gradior Cognitive? ▪ What is the ideal usage scenario for you?

Figure 14. Gradior Cognitive co-creation session at INTRAS

Data collection phase 2: Small scale pilot study

The small-scale pilot phase was conducted at the Parquesol centre of the INTRAS Foundation, located at C/Martín Santos Romero N° 1 (247016, Valladolid). Five therapists and 52 end-users were pre-selected by professionals from the INTRAS Neuropsychology Clinic. These professionals selected participants based on clinical and neuropsychological evaluations, adhering to inclusion criteria: include individuals over 55 with voluntary participation, preserved understanding and consent capability, mild cognitive impairment or early-stage dementia, with MMSE scores between ≥ 21 and ≤ 27 , indicating significant memory or thinking issues beyond normal aging but not severely impacting daily activities. Exclusion criteria encompass severe sensory disorders (significant hearing or vision impairments), inability to comprehend or consent, psychiatric conditions or neurological disorders limiting study participation, substance abuse (alcoholism or alcohol-related dementia), and antipsychotic medication use.

The distribution of end-users comprised two groups: an experimental group consisting of 40 individuals (age 57 to 91 years; 23 women and 17 men) and a small control group consisting of 8 individuals (age 63 to 85 years; 3 women and 5 men).

An experimental design study was employed, incorporating a control group (which received no intervention and only underwent assessments), with pre-test, and post-test phases. To ensure the internal validity of the study, clinical scales and personalized questionnaires, such as the MMSE (Mini-Mental State Examination), Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MOCA), Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS), UCLA Loneliness Scale, LUBBEN Social Life Scale, General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE), Quality of Life (EQ-5D-3L), User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ), and System Usability Scale (SUS), were utilized.

Additionally, data was gathered through the Gradior cognitive program, using the Gradior Score, a quantitative measure summarizing monthly performance in each subcategory and globally. Qualitative information was collected through open questions directed to professionals and users after the pilot intervention.

The intervention administered to participants, spanning a duration of 3-4 months, comprehended sessions of 30-minute cognitive stimulation with the Gradior Cognitive program. This program included audiovisual exercises addressing various cognitive functions, such as attention, memory, and calculation, with variable sub functions and difficulty levels. The naturalistic approach of the intervention facilitated users' access to cognitive stimulation sessions through their own tablets, enabling daily engagement.

Figure 15. End-users in interaction with the Gradior Cognitive

2.3.2 Execution and Challenges

Recruitment:

Selected end-users were contacted by professionals from the Memory Clinic of the INTRAS Foundation. These professionals identified potential participants based on clinical information and neuropsychological profiles. Subsequently, a selection process was carried out in accordance with the inclusion and exclusion criteria defined for the study, through face-to-face interviews, where the study's objectives, characteristics, and participation were explained. A concerted effort was made to inclusively involve participants from both urban and rural areas, which required the definition of action protocols for the duly management of requirements and challenges such as coordinating follow-ups, remotely monitoring and solving system incidences (if occurring).

The execution of the study during the summer season presented supplementary challenges. In several instances, some participants were distanced from their homes or dedicated their time to different activities, deviating from their usual routines.

Ethics and legislation:

The study has been conducted in agreement with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and the guidelines for good clinical practices, subjecting the protocol to scrutiny by the clinical research ethics committee for approval (approval code: PI 22-2569 NO HCUV). Each participant received a comprehensive document delineating their rights in accordance with data protection laws, providing them the opportunity to engage in discussions about informed consent with the study coordinators. Rigorous practices have been established, covering the formulation of an ethical protocol, the acquisition of informed consent from participants, and the safeguarding of data privacy and security, all in alignment with the guidelines for responsible research.

Ultimately, the methodology employed was the subject of specific adjustments. The general self-efficacy questionnaire was removed, and a questionnaire assessing system usability (SUS) was introduced. The UEQ questionnaire was replaced by a shorter version to prevent participants' fatigue.

Due to the concise pilot period (3-4 months), the interim evaluation was omitted as significant changes were not anticipated within such short durations of Gradior Cognitive use.

2.3.3 Outcomes and Analysis

Throughout the study, qualitative data was gathered (during the co-creation sessions and post-piloting in semi-structured interviews), and quantitative data were collected through the mentioned questionnaires. The analysis of qualitative data and the statistical analysis of quantitative data are detailed below.

Co-creation sessions:

Users emphasize the importance of incorporating technologies nowadays, stating that it is indeed essential in daily life. Regarding the cognitive stimulation program, they emphasize the crucial nature of an initial adaptation period to the use of technology during the sessions. Their satisfaction with Gradior Cognitive is clearly expressed, particularly in terms of the treatment delivered, emphasising its capacity to respond to their specific needs. Nevertheless, users occasionally highlight that traditional rehabilitation provides them greater flexibility, allowing more time for responsiveness and error correction.

The preference for human contact is emphasized by users, both in the context of traditional rehabilitation and when utilizing technologies. When sessions are conducted in their homes, users acknowledge the need for follow-up to prompt adherence to exercises until a routine is established. Despite recognizing their adaptability to technologies, they assert that these should serve as a complement to the individually tailored therapy directly provided by professionals.

Throughout the sessions, professionals shared challenges prevalent in the rehabilitation field, encompassing prolonged waiting times in the public domain to access resources and many challenges in the services coordination making very difficult to implement integrative care models.

From the perspective of professionals, there is agreement that the incorporation of technology into rehabilitation processes yields substantial benefits. Notable interest is observed in public sector to promote the deployment of technologies for home-based rehabilitation. The increasing acceptance of technologies in health and social services is regarded as an indicator of advancements in this field. What was initially perceived as an additional workload has swiftly demonstrated its efficacy, contributing to the widespread of this perspective.

In response to Gradior Cognitive, professionals underscore the significance of remote monitoring when conducting rehabilitation from home and stress the meticulous adaptation of technologies to each individual's profile. They also provide insights into the possibilities offered by this software, such as its potential for conducting rehabilitation in rural settings and attending to a larger number of patients.

Small scale pilot:

In the analysis of the results of the pilot study with Gradior Cognitive software, significant findings emerge in various areas. Specifically, a correlation has been observed between the results of the MOCA and MMSE tests, indicating that higher scores on the MMSE are associated with superior performance on the MOCA. While the significance is subtle, it suggests a trend of change that could be more pronounced with a more extended pilot period or an increase in the number of participants. Additionally, a decrease in the perception of loneliness after Gradior treatment was evident, according to the UCLA scale, indicating a positive impact on the emotional well-being of the participants.

Regarding usability assessments, mixed results were noted. Although higher cognitive functions' scores were associated with a better user experience according to the UEQ test, the SUS test revealed that higher MMSE scores were related to lower usability of the program. Furthermore, a relation between gender and education was identified in the SUS test, where participants with basic education showed stability in usability scores, while those with medium levels of education and male gender gave higher scores. The Gradior Cognitive program demonstrated positive results, particularly in maintaining cognitive functions and reducing the perception of loneliness.

Gradior Cognitive is appreciated for its ability to establish routines and mitigate cognitive decline. Its customization capabilities, training, and integration of meaningful activities are seen as avenues to improve the patient experience and alleviate the professional workload. To optimize Gradior Cognitive, it is suggested to prioritize the incorporation new valuable customizable functionalities features, intensify professional training to leverage these features, diversify activity options, and expand its application to new healthcare settings. This approach positions Gradior Cognitive as a versatile tool included by healthcare professionals within the category of health and well-being programs.

2.3.4 Conclusions

The pilot study on Gradior Cognitive has highlighted the significant potential of integrating technological programs into the rehabilitation processes for older adults. Both qualitative and quantitative data suggest that using Gradior Cognitive can support with positive effects or extending maintenance of cognitive abilities both in the results of the cognitive performance in the cognitive areas and domains trained through the digital tool and assessed in the cognitive evaluations. A reduction in the perception of loneliness was observed post-treatment with Gradior, particularly as the participants' age increased. This indicates that Gradior Cognitive not only assists in cognitive stimulation but also plays a role in improving emotional well-being among older adults.

Healthcare professionals have recognized the program's benefits in establishing routines and decelerating cognitive decline. However, they advocate for its incorporation into an integrated care model, emphasizing the necessity for customizable training and applications.

The study further underscores the essential role of user experience and satisfaction in adopting and effectively using such technologies. Moreover, it highlights the importance of a continuous feedback loop from both users and professionals to ensure the program evolves to meet ongoing needs.

Recommendations and Lessons Learned

The study underlines the importance of a user-centred design in technology-assisted rehabilitation. It reaffirms that technological interventions should complement, rather than replace, traditional rehabilitation methods, thereby preserving the invaluable element of human (and professional) interaction.

The necessity for adaptability and flexibility in the program's design is crucial to cater to diverse user needs and abilities, stressing the importance of integrating these technologies within a broader healthcare ecosystem. Finally, it highlighted the specific challenges of remote rehabilitation, including user engagement and technical issues, pointing towards the need for innovative solutions and robust support mechanisms. Future research should aim for broader studies and incorporate emerging and integrative technologies to elevate cognitive rehabilitation's impact.

In particular, the study revealed that gender and education level influenced usability scores, with male participants and those with a medium level of education rating the program's usability higher. This finding underscores the need to consider demographic factors in the program's design and training, ensuring accessibility and effectiveness for a broader user base.

For future endeavours, it is recommended that studies involve larger sample sizes and extended pilot durations to assess Gradior Cognitive long-term impacts on cognitive functions and emotional well-being more comprehensively. Moreover, integrating innovative technologies, such as virtual reality components of the Gradior Suite, could significantly augment the efficacy of cognitive rehabilitation programs.

2.4 Case Study 4 - Virtual Mirror therapy (LiCalab/Belgium)

2.4.1 Study description

Objective

The initial objective of the current study was to assess the non-inferiority of virtual mirror therapy as compared to standard mirror therapy in subacute and chronic stroke patients, as well as to assess user experience of the virtual mirror therapy from the perspective of both patients and clinicians. After the protocol adaptation, we rephrased the objective into assessing user experience and usability of virtual mirror therapy from the perspective of both rehabilitation patients and clinicians.

Preparation & deployment

In line with the other JRA studies we decided to focus on stroke patients. The aim was to include 10 to 20 sub-acute and chronic patients and 4 to 12 clinicians (doctor, nurse, occupational therapist, physiotherapist, psychologist, etc.) at the rehabilitation centre in Geel, Belgium. We reached out to acquainted clinicians of the local hospital from LiCalab's community panel for recruitment of both clinicians and patients. Ethics approval for the study protocol was obtained from the ethical committee of Antwerp University Hospital in Belgium (UZA), as well as the local ethical committee of the hospital in Geel.

After adaptation of the pilot protocol five patients, aged 20 to 67, were included for the VR demo session: four stroke patients with hemiplegia of which two experienced spasms, and one rehabilitation patient with arm and shoulder amputation. Each of them used the VR app for 30 minutes.

Data collection phase 1: Co-creation

Seven care professionals took part in the co-creation session on October 18, 2022. Their current experience with (intervention) technology as well as their attitude towards technology was assessed. A demonstration of the VR application prototype was presented and clinicians gave their feedback on possible advantages and limitations of using this and other technology in their work.

Figure 16. VR therapy co-creation session with care professionals

Data collection phase 2: Small scale pilot study

This small-scale pilot study was conducted by LiCalab and Mobilab & Care in Belgium. Mirror therapy is a rehabilitation method during which a mirror is placed between the arms or legs of a patient in order to create the illusion that a patients' affected limb is moving when the patients sees his or her unaffected limb moving in the mirror. For the study, we aimed at recruiting 20 stroke patients and their caregivers (doctor, nurse, occupational therapist, physiotherapist, psychologist, etc.) and weekly test them using a virtual mirror rehabilitation app prototype for a period of 8 weeks.

After adaptation of the protocol, the study was set-up as a one-time demo session testing user experience of the commercially available VR app CUREO® in five rehabilitation patients.

Figure 17. VR demo session in rehabilitation patients (left usual therapy, right mirrored therapy)

2.4.2 Execution and Challenges

Recruitment

The Living lab panel manager manages LiCalab's panel comprising not only healthy citizens and patients, but also professional care givers. The panel manager reached out to several clinicians from the existing panel to present the study protocol in the hospitals in the neighbourhood. This way, a collaboration with Algemeen Ziekenhuis Geel was established. The existing relationship of trust with these clinicians helped in the recruitment of both care professionals as well as rehabilitation patients for the study.

Ethics and legislation

Firstly, with the introduction of the European Medical Device Regulation (MDR) in 2021, technological applications used in a medical context may be considered medical devices. Because of the recent introduction of this legislation, ethical committees did not have (much) prior experience with handling such protocol applications in a research context, resulting in a very cautious approach.

Secondly, submission of the protocol needed to be done both on a local and central ethical committee level. Application of the protocol at the first central ethical committee (Gasthuiszusters Antwerpen, GZA) did not result in approval because of uncertainties regarding correct interpretation of the MDR. Hence, a submission was sent to the ethical committee of Antwerp University Hospital (UZA). After revision, the ethical application was approved. On the local level, we presented the study protocol in-person to the ethics committee of Algemeen Ziekenhuis Geel. The whole process of ethical approval took more time than anticipated.

Extra workshop

The clinicians that participated in the co-creation session were very enthusiastic about the use of VR in a rehabilitation context. Due to time restrictions, only a short demonstration of the VR prototype app was given by LiCalab and Mobilab&Care staff during the first co-creation session on October 18, 2022. As some care professionals expressed the wish to use and try the VR app themselves, an extra workshop was organised on December 15, 2022. About 10 clinicians and interns participated in this session.

Figure 18. Clinicians testing the VR prototype app

Protocol adjustment

Just before the start of the study in January 2023, clinicians informed us that they changed their minds and would no longer participate in the proposed study. The main reason was the VR app prototype containing bugs, sometimes resulting in closing and reopening the app in the middle of an exercise. Clinicians were afraid these bugs would frustrate the patients who already experienced a lot of challenges during their rehabilitation.

Several options were explored. Unfortunately, building an updated version of the original application as well as using an off-the-shelf commercial app for the original protocol were too expensive. We ended up with a compromise: The German organisation CUREosity that had built the commercial app CUREO[®] was willing to let us use their app for a one time demo session in exchange for a market introduction in the Belgian hospital market. The VR therapy application supports cognitive and sensorimotor rehabilitation. It consists of six modules that can be adapted to the patient's training needs and can be used in regular as well as mirrored therapy. Hence, in the morning we were able to test user experience and usability in five rehabilitation patients, and in the afternoon we organised a demo session for Belgian clinicians and hospital staff which we recruited with the help of our panel managers. The disadvantage of the protocol adaptation was that we were not able to test rehabilitation progression over time. Consequently, we couldn't make any statements on the non-inferiority of VR mirror therapy as compared to usual mirror therapy.

2.4.3 Outcomes and Analysis

Co-creation

The care professionals in our sessions reported to be quite open to the use of technology in a rehabilitation context. However, they currently face the following thresholds: A first issue is ignorance. Often clinicians are absorbed by their daily routine and are not aware of all the

technological possibilities: what can technology offer, what could be the impact of the use of technological innovations etc. In addition, care givers expressed their concerns with regard to using technology in older patients or patients with severe cognitive impairments. Another challenge is the cost that comes with investing in technological innovations and persuading the people that make decisions on what hospital money is spent on.

A huge benefit of using VR therapy is the large variety of exercises and environments without the need for actual relocation, e.g. crossing the street or going to the supermarket can be practiced without extra time investments or actual risks. Furthermore, the exercises are relevant for daily activities. It's more than just playing a game, although the game component adds to the patients' motivation. The therapist can follow on the screen what the patient is seeing or doing and can intervene at any time.

Small scale pilot study

A short summary of the results is provided. A more elaborate report can be provided upon request (kim.helsen@thomasmore.be). The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) was used to assess user experience. The UEQ contains 6 scales with 26 items:

- 1) Attractiveness: Overall impression of the product. Do users like or dislike the product?
- 2) Perspicuity: Is it easy to get familiar with the product? Is it easy to learn how to use the product?
- 3) Efficiency: Can users solve their tasks without unnecessary effort?
- 4) Dependability: Does the user feel in control of the interaction?
- 5) Stimulation: Is it exciting and motivating to use the product?
- 6) Novelty: Is the product innovative and creative? Does the product catch the interest of users?

Figure 19. Comparison of the CUREO results with the data in the benchmark

As shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**Figure 19, the CUREO application scores excellent compared to other applications in the benchmark of 452 innovative solutions on almost all items. Only the dependability of the CUREO application scores a bit less but is still above average. Both patients and clinicians were enthusiastic about using the app complementary to regular rehabilitation therapy.

2.4.4 Conclusions

Recommendations and Lessons Learned

All patients enthusiastically confirmed that the game component of the VR therapy exercises boosts motivation and therapy compliance. The alternation of exercises and VR environments makes them forget about time and the fact that they are engaged in therapy exercises. An additional advantage is that no prior experience is required to use the app. Moreover, the therapist was surprised to see that the extra motivation resulted in a bigger range of motion in some patients compared to the traditional exercises. The mirror therapy option was also tested and worked good in some modules, but with the current adapted protocol it is not sure whether this type of mirror therapy has the same effect as traditional mirror therapy. More research is needed to confirm the non-inferiority of virtual mirror therapy for stroke patients as well as for patients with upper limb amputation in comparison with traditional mirror therapy. Another advantage is that several patients can perform different exercises under supervision of one physiotherapist at the same time. Intensity or level of difficulty can be adjusted automatically with build-in algorithms of the app or can be adjusted by the therapist, based on his expertise or patient's feedback.

In summary, VR rehabilitation exercises offer a pleasant change to complement existing rehabilitation therapies for patients. Also care professionals confirm that the use of VR therapy can add value to the rehabilitation trajectory in addition to existing therapy and under supervision of the therapist.

We learned to reserve enough time for ethics approval, as it may take a while to obtain. The network or panel of the sustainable Living Lab provided added value in the recruitment phase (establish a hospital collaboration through clinicians that were already part of the living lab community) and when changes to the protocol were required (reach out to clinicians of other hospitals for the demonstration of the app as an introduction to the Belgian hospital market). The existing relationship of trust with the clinicians made it possible to search for a win-win situation and adjust the protocol when the original study no longer seemed feasible.

2.5 Case Study 5 - Teledance (McGill-UdeM-CRIR LL/ Canada)

2.5.1 Study description

Objective

The objective of this project was to test and the teledance intervention (a series of video dance vignettes that have been adapted for stroke rehabilitation) with a group of potential users (i.e. people with stroke and clinicians) to identify and help resolve problems that may influence their experience and to explore the potential impacts of adding the intervention to usual care.

By testing the intervention within an intensive functional rehabilitation setting, the objective was to identify the characteristics of users to whom such an intervention can be applied, evaluate its usability and safety, and explore its potential impacts.

Preparation

No Co-creation sessions were carried out as part of the project. Ethics approval was obtained from Research Ethics Board (REB) en readaptation et en déficience physique in Montreal, Canada.

The aim was to offer teledance intervention to patients during their stay in the hospital. Teledance consists of video vignettes delivered via the OpenTera software platform on an iPad as well as follow-up modalities offered via OpenTera or other means. Each video vignettes was ± 10 minutes long and offered thematic content (postural control, coordination, fine motor skills and communication) to be

performed in a sitting position. A combination of 3 video vignettes made up each teledance session, for a total of 30 minutes per session. Users were instructed to perform teledance 4 times per week for approximately 2 hours of dance per week. Follow-up sessions (user-clinician, user-research team member, clinician-research team member) were also included.

Small Scale Pilot Study:

Participants

Patients were recruited from two rehabilitation sites in Montreal, Canada. Their admission to the stroke program was recent (≤ 14 days). The type of stroke, its location, the degree of functional impairment, and the age of the users were not exclusion criteria; only the ones who could not participate in this type of intervention autonomously and safely after an initial assisted introduction, aggressive patients, or those with known symptoms of dementia and Alzheimer's before the stroke were excluded. Their participation was voluntary, and they needed to have sufficient cognitive abilities to give informed consent and follow instructions. All users taking part in the research were able to understand and express themselves in French.

Evaluations performed

Some evaluations were carried out before and after each teledance session, others once a week, and others at the end of the intervention. Each teledance session was recorded (video) via the OpenTera platform.

Participation Frequency and Time, and motor engagement time (appropriate & inappropriate)

- Video recording (after each session)

Fatigue

- Likert Scale 1-10 (before and after each session)

Pain

- Likert Scale 1-10 (before and after each session)

Enjoyment and Usability

- Likert Scale 1-7 (once a week)

Acceptability of Intervention Measure (AIM)

- Weiner Measures Questionnaire (at the end of the intervention)

Intervention Appropriateness Measure (IAM)

- Weiner Measures Questionnaire (at the end of the intervention)

Feasibility of Intervention Measure (FIM)

- Weiner Measures Questionnaire (at the end of the intervention)

Experience and Perceived Impacts

- Semi-structured individual interview (at the end of the intervention)

2.5.2 Execution and Challenges

Progress and Barriers

To date, seven (n=7) patients were identified and screened. Of these, five (n=5) were enrolled and completed the project. The remaining two (n=2) did not meet the inclusion criteria and could not participate. No clinicians have yet been recruited for the study.

Recruitment and retainment of research personnel were a significant challenge for this project. Teledance was implemented in two rehabilitation centers. Given the post-COVID-19 context in the province of Québec, having access to clinicians to evaluate the intervention proved to be impossible due to these centres being severely short-staffed. While clinicians expressed their interest in the project, ultimately, they could not be liberated from the regular clinical hours to participate. Furthermore, there was difficulty in retaining staff that could implement the intervention. Over the course of the project, many research assistants were trained to administer the teledance intervention, a process that involved significant effort and time commitment from the lead researcher. However, due to unforeseen circumstances, most had to leave the project causing significant delays in testing. This also led to the financial resources that had been secured for the project to be depleted earlier than expected.

Unfortunately, the lead researcher also had to take a leave of absence for health reasons recently, which is another significant barrier to this project. While the project is still ongoing despite this, it is advancing more slowly than anticipated.

2.5.3 Outcomes and Analysis

Analysis:

Analysis of the various data collected is currently underway.

2.5.4 Conclusions

Recommendations and Lessons Learned:

At this time, we are unable to make any firm conclusions regarding whether the addition of the teledance intervention to the usual rehabilitation of stroke survivors improves patients' recovery. However, the fact that the five participants enrolled in the study were able to complete the protocol suggests that the intervention is feasible. While measures of the patients' subjective experience are still being analysed, clinical impression suggests that their overall the intervention was appreciated.

Lessons learned include the fact that bringing a new intervention into a clinical setting required a lot of coordination with program directors. In normal times (i.e. not right post-COVID-19) deploying a project in this setting would have been potentially challenging. However, the current climate of units that are short-staffed posed a significant challenge to the timely advancement of the project. That being said, the project, while currently on hold, is expected to resume in the coming months with the recruitment of additional participants and of clinicians.

2.6 Case Study 6 - Augmented Gait training (WALKAGAIN) Study description

2.6.1 Study description

Objective and Phases: The main objective of this pilot study is to assess the effect of adding augmented gait training to usual rehabilitation and technology targeting the walking abilities of individuals admitted to rehabilitation post-stroke in single, dual and multitasking conditions. A secondary objective is to establish an international common data set for standing mobility

assessment and conceptualize the common elements (dose, progression...) of the training protocols in order to be able to compare findings data between sites and/or analyze them together. To do so, a pre-post pragmatic design with a blind outcome assessment was set up to assess the performance of participants using augmented training protocols as compared to a control group and/or previously collected data (if available). The findings from two Montreal Metropolitan (Canada) rehabilitation sites (Jewish rehabilitation Hospital and Institut de réadaptation Gingras-Lindsay-de-Montréal) will be pooled together to assess the overall effect of the concepts of augmented gait training.

Before starting the project, a required step was to meet with the clinicians of the stroke units in order to agree on a minimum clinical data set based on already used assessments to identify the process of allocation to the training protocols and to establish the guidelines for the dose and progression of the locomotor training. We also needed to agree on the main outcomes for appraising that the participants walk better and safer in the community. A co-creation session was thus held with clinicians, researchers and program director where the process and different interventions were discussed.

2.6.2 Execution and Challenges

Progress and Barriers: So far, the co-creation session has been successfully completed with recruitment and intervention currently underway in both CRIR Living Labs. The co-creation session was held at the Jewish rehabilitation Hospital on June 21 2023 and was led by a physiotherapist who is associated to the study. A total of nine people participated: eight clinicians with a speciality in stroke rehabilitation and one stroke program director. Additionally, seven members of the research team (researchers, clinicians and coordinators) observed the session while it was occurring.

The main challenge encountered to date is linked to the functional and physical status of the stroke patients that hinders their participation in some of the interventions. Researchers and clinicians are problem solving together and personalizing the interventions to accommodate for individual challenges and limitations.

2.6.3 Outcomes and Analysis

Evaluation and KPIs:

Sample

Sample. Twelve to fifteen stroke patients will be recruited in each site from the stroke units of the two sites for each locomotor training protocol. Participants are selected for their potential to improve gait capacities and according to the requirements of their individual goals for improvement.

At the JRH site, inclusion criteria are: 1) having a stroke and being in rehabilitation, 2) having initiated the gait training with or without assistive devices, with or without human assistance 3) tolerating one hour of exercise with breaks, 4) in the presence of aphasia showing no more than mild or mild to moderate impairment, 5) having a reliable Yes/No. Exclusion criteria will include major pain ($\geq 7/10$ on VAS including pain from severe orthopedic conditions such as lower limb osteoarthritis), - severe cognitive deficits defined as an inability to understand instructions or MoCA below 20/30, and comorbid conditions interfering with locomotion and cognition, as verified by medical records. cardiorespiratory problems and other medical and cognitive conditions that could affect the ability to understand instructions. The cut-off MoCA score was decided in collaboration with the clinicians, as a higher cut-off would exclude the majority of our inpatient stroke clientele and affect the feasibility of the study. We also collect data on usability, feasibility and opinions from clinicians about the training interventions through questionnaires and/or interviews. All participants have to sign the consent form which will have been approved by the ethics committee of the CRIR.

Intervention

Intervention. Three major technologies (either individually or combined) are used for the locomotor training: biomechanical (e.g., split belt training, walking with loaded segment, ascending slope), haptic (e.g., vibrations) and virtual reality (virtual environment) (Figure 5). The precise locomotor training protocol is decided by the clinicians in consultation with the researchers and takes into consideration the preferences of the participants (after phase 1). All locomotor training includes cognitive/language tasks as well attention demanding tasks, implemented gradually from simple to more complex (single, dual, and multitasking) while the gait training will also be progressed. The training consists of, for example, 30 minutes of walking or doing a number of steps, using the selected protocol with 5 min. of warming up and 5 min. of recovery. Participants are allowed to take breaks if their heart rate exceeds 60% of their maximal heart rate or they reported an exertion of 5 on the Borg rating scale which represents severe exertion (Borg et al, 1982). The training is restarted when the participant's heart rate lowers back to its level at rest. The augmented gait training is given twice a week for 10 sessions (five weeks). Prior to each training session, participant's heart rate (e.g., Polar electro Oy) and blood pressure is taken at rest. The age-related maximum heart rate is be calculated using the Karvonen Formula (Pescatello et al, 2014).

Figure 20 Examples of technologies for augmented gait training: (A) split-belt training, (B) vibrations, (C) virtual reality.

Details of Locomotor training:

1) Biomechanical constraints (e.g. Error augmentation training. Gait perturbation)

Error augmentation training: Participants walk on a split-belt configuration with a belt speed ratio of 2:1 (slower belt set to comfortable speed). The leg with the shorter step length (SL) walked on the faster belt (fast leg) (Betschart et al, 2018). Therefore, for participants with a shorter paretic SL, the paretic leg was on the fast belt and vice versa for participants with shorter non-paretic SL. Comfortable belt speed is tested and adjusted prior to each training session by increasing or decreasing speeds of both belts in 0.05m/s intervals until comfortable speed is attained. The participants are motivated to achieve 20 minutes of split-belt walking and are allowed to take breaks. After the 20 minutes of split-belt walking, participants walk again at tied-belt configuration. This period served as a cooling down period and for safety so that participants do not pass directly to walking over ground. During the entire training on the SBT, participants can wear a safety harness without body-weight support and are allowed to hold the handrails. This protocol can be done with an inclined surface or a load can be placed just above the ankle to increase the difficulties of walking (Duclos et al, 2014).

Gait perturbation: Using the split-belt treadmill, one can generate perturbations during gait by increasing or decreasing the speed of one belt during one gait cycle (Esmaeili et al, 2020). It stimulates a slip (faster belt) or a trip (slower belt). These perturbations are applied at random steps (every 6-12 steps) and can be applied on one side or on both sides. In addition, the type of perturbation (slip or trip) can be applied repeatedly or randomly. Repeated perturbations targets adaptation to a specific perturbation (mostly proactive adaptation), while random perturbations targets more reactive adaptations. Training trials generally include 10 repeated or 16 random perturbations. Intensity of the perturbation can be varied with various extent of changes in speed, relatively to the comfortable gait speed used between perturbations. Progression can be done from repeated, low intensity perturbation on one side to random, high intensity perturbations on both sides. There is currently no recommendation on the number of perturbations required to significantly improve balance. We obtained clinically relevant results with a mean of 150 perturbations per session, for 9 sessions in chronic stroke participants (initial walking speed between as low as 0.39 m/s and initial MiniBESTest of 11/28).

2) Haptic feedback (e.g. vibrations, avatars)

Muscle vibration: Using vibrators applied bilaterally on the flexors and extensors of the hips, knees and ankles, one can generate sensory activity that would be associated with the movements of gait, in individuals who are not moving, in a sitting or standing position. It generates a perception of gait movements at various cadences, from slow to general-population step frequency (up to 120 steps/minutes) (Tapin et al, 2021). For training purposes, one can set goals on the number of steps to be simulated with the system, at a target frequency higher than the participant can produce voluntarily. The muscle stimulation is completed by a VR system that displays the gait movements of a self-avatar synchronised with the muscle sensory information. The participants thus see and feel their lower-limbs moving at a cadence they cannot achieve voluntarily (Labbé et al, 2021). In addition, the participant can try to match the perceived movement with voluntary-produced stepping-in-place movement to produce gait like motor activity facilitated by the sensory stimulation. At 120 steps/minutes, one can simulate 2000 steps in less than 17 minutes of training without break.

3) Virtual Reality (VR) intervention for augmented gait training

Functional community ambulation must target multiple dimensions of gait while adapting to the task goals and environment, including the demands due to distance, temporal, and ambient conditions as well as terrain, physical load, postural transition, attentional requirements and density and collisions (Shumway-Cook and Woollacott, 2017). These multiple dimensions can be trained over-ground with a headset, or by using a specialized treadmill. The C-Mill (van Ooijen et al, 2015), which is an oversized instrumented treadmill (walking area 70 x 300 cm) incorporating visual and auditory cues. They can also be trained on the Infinadeck, an omnidirectional platform that allows changes of speed and direction while walking (Soni and Lamontagne, 2020). It enables visuo-locomotor training in a controlled and safe manner. The treatment protocols are modifiable and controllable through computer software. While training on the C-Mill, moving images are projected onto the treadmill, incorporating visually guided stepping, speeding up/slowing down, obstacle negotiation, and gait-adaptability games. In combination with a large television screen displaying the moving environment in front, the training can include cognitive-locomotor dual/multi-tasking, such as walking while attending to street signs or messages in the presence or absence of distractors. The messages can be words that the participants are asked to recognize as words in French (or English) or not while walking (dual-tasking) or while walking in the presence of distractors (multitasking). While training on the Infinadeck, participants are immersed in virtual environment viewed in a head mounted display and can train on dimensions such as changing walking speeds, walking distances, obstacle circumvention, postural transitions and dual-task walking.

Data collection

Standardized outcomes is collected in the week before from the inpatient team's admission notes (T1) and the discharge notes week after (T2) including participant satisfaction on the locomotor training. If the patient's function has markedly progressed since the admission evaluation, the outcome measures is re-done by the clinician researcher. We also implement a follow-up assessment at 6 months (telephone call; T3). Data is selected according to the Canadian Best Practice Recommendations for Stroke Care (CBPRSC; [Lindsay et al, 2010] and covers all dimensions of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF). The principal outcomes are "walking in the community" (shopping, visiting a museum, walking in the street, etc.) and participants' satisfaction assessed at T3. Each participant is assessed pre and post intervention to establish their single and dual tasking abilities and subsequently measure improvement following intervention. This assessment includes assessment of walking (single), walking and reading words or short phrases and walking in the presence of distractors. The ICF includes many dimensions of life (personal factors, body structures and functions, activities and participation) with impact on a person's quality of life and well-being (McDougall et al, 2010). Demographic data is collected at admission (e.g., age, gender, weight, height, stroke information). In addition, clinical data is collected at admission (T1), discharge (T2) and some at follow-up (T3), to assess changes in loss of sensation, tone (Modified Ashworth Scale), sensorimotor deficits (Chedoke-McMaster Stroke Assessment), pain (Visual Analogue Scale), muscle strength (Medical Research Council Manual Muscle Testing scale), mobility (balance (Berg Balance Scale or Mini-BEST Test), gait impairments speed (10-meter walk test), endurance (6MWT), dual task (TUG cognitive), etc.), cognitive/language evaluation of participant and their emotions, aspirations and achievement gaps (Patient-Specific Functional Scale) (Fugl-Meyer et al, 2002).

Analysis: The study is currently underway, 4 people are currently participating. Hence the proposed data analysis is provided here.

Data Analysis: We will apply the minimal important clinical difference (when known) for the measures to estimate meaningful change in performance. The statistical approach will also vary to meet the needs of the studies. Overall, descriptive statistics will be presented for demographic information, stroke characteristics, the number of breaks and perceived exertion during training (modified Borg Scale). Normal distribution will be tested with the Shapiro-Wilk test. The effect of training over time (pre-, post-, follow-up evaluation) on dependent variables will be tested with repeated-measures parametric or non-parametric tests. Effect sizes of changes found between evaluations will be computed using Hedges's *g* (Lakens, 2013), which is a Cohen's *d* value corrected for the sample size using means, SDs and sample sizes and recommended for small samples. These *g* scores can be interpreted the same way as the Cohen's *d* scores: *g* around 0.2 is interpreted as "low", 0.5 "average" and 0.8 as "strong".

2.6.4 Conclusions

Recommendations and Lessons Learned: Given that the study is currently underway, no conclusions are available to date.

Recommendations and Lessons Learned: Given the early stage of the study it is difficult to make recommendations other than to impress on the importance of synergistic activity between researchers and clinicians as they problem solve to adjust interventions to the individual functional and physical status of the stroke patients participating in the study.

2.7 Case Study 7 Co-creation study (Tregag/Hungary)

2.7.1 Study description and execution

Objective and Phases: At this phase of the study Tregag was only responsible for the co-creation session, so this report does not include notes on pilots.

The aim of the co-creation session was to understand how health professionals (or those working outside the health system but within the health care system) and patients evaluate the current functioning of rehabilitation in terms of:

- technological infrastructure (tools),
- openness to technology (attitudes).

The aim of this study was to find out what suggestions caretakers and facilitators have in relation to the current situation, what tools, technological (and other) possibilities they see to help rehabilitation, to increase its efficiency and effectiveness.

For the co-creation sessions the following steps were taken: identification of stakeholders participating in the activity, identification of places for co-creation session, carrying out co-creation session, summarizing and analysing findings. There was one facilitator of the co-creation sessions, who conducted the focus group session or the individual interviews. In the session health care professionals, people in private rehabilitation structures and patients took part. For those who were not able to speak in a group, we asked questions based on the information we had already obtained from others, trying to make up for not speaking in a group.

2.7.2 Outcomes and Analysis/ Conclusions

The general picture of knowledge about the use of IT/electronic devices is that older people are less open in general and less familiar with these devices - however, health actors also said and confirmed that they rarely see an older patient who does not have a smartphone. (That said, it is not yet possible to expect today that it is sufficient to focus exclusively on phone devices.)

It is important that the information/motivational material should be produced at different levels, so that everyone can find the right information, making rehabilitation inclusive.

As for health workers, they are so overloaded by work that they hardly have time to learn to use new technical devices and they would need some update on them. Especially it would be essential to have educational materials that are linked to the patient's story also applying smart tools for its facilitation.

As for rehabilitation professionals outside of the public health care system the use of technology and smart tools were expressed especially in the fields of making connection between them and the patient and them and doctors. Collaboration with professionals within the health system (both in general and in relation to specific patients) should be supported by smart apps. Much more emphasis should be placed on health promotion and information/education.

As for patients, there is little information available on rehabilitation, and those who are not familiar with the health system are completely lost in it. According to the interviewees, rehabilitation is rarely recommended by specialists themselves, and a change of attitude is needed. Mental health support is not offered by the health system in the event of a major illness or accident and is almost only available to very well-informed patients.

There should be more and better information flow between doctor and patient about the options. Current communication practices are power-based, making it difficult to decide between possible and offered treatments. Smart tools and technologies facilitating this above process would be desperately needed.

Barriers: The way of reaching practitioners for the interview was made complicated by bureaucratic issues. Thus, after long procedures, we had to select a new set of interviewees as the legal and other procedures of one rehabilitation centre made it impossible to conduct interviews with their

practitioners, though we had their individual consent. In the end co-creation sessions were organized in smaller groups of 2-3 people and participants were led through a set of open questions and could diverge from the original path of conversation if needed.

3 Harmonized Analysis across Living Labs

3.1 Living Lab Harmonized services

3.1.1 Objective and Phases:

The aim of the JRA collaboration was to cocreate and test a harmonized research protocol for developing co-creation and piloting phase.

3.1.2 Execution and Challenges

Progress and Barriers: “Expert opinions and advisory services” from the Living Lab were utilized to collect data on each Living Lab device. “Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping” services were employed to identify external expert panel members for the Delphi-panel. Additionally, “Small-scale real-life testing” services were indirectly utilized, as the JRA case studies provided real-life data on the usage of data collection devices in various settings. This data forms the foundation for evaluating the possibilities of creating hybrid personas.

The study was conducted as follows: First, the existing devices to collect qualitative and quantitative data via digital biomarkers or tools were identified among all three JRAs living labs. Second, small-scale JRA case studies were conducted to evaluate the applicability of the selected tools to collect digital biomarkers or other data in various rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday living environment settings. In parallel to case studies, modified online Delphi-study was conducted to define a taxonomy to categorize and organize the digital data collection and intervention tools employed by the case studies. Third, after completion of the case studies, the utilized devices were mapped according to taxonomy classification and examples on measurements and measurement intervals were collected to identify the possibilities for big data–driven hybrid persona creation. Finally, the challenges and benefits of using the devices to collect digital biomarker data were discussed with the case studies.

3.1.3 Outcomes and Analysis

Evaluation and KPIs: Consensus regarding the category definitions, whether definition was easy to understand and whether the item belongs to subcategory was measured by strongly disagree, disagree, agree, strongly agree, and no answer Likert-scale. The KPI for consensus was set to 70 % or higher agreement level for supermajority agreement and 80 % or higher for strong supermajority agreement.

Analysis: The resulting taxonomy includes 52 subcategories in three different layers. The first layer makes separation between 'data monitoring and collection' and 'intervention technologies'. The first one is then further divided into 'environmental' and 'human monitoring' and the latter one to 'Assistive technology,' 'Extended reality – XR (VR & AR)' and 'Serious games'. Only the 'human monitoring' includes the third layer, which consist of 'biometrics,' 'activity and behavioural monitoring,' 'cognitive ability and mental processes,' 'electrical biosignals and physiological monitoring measures,' '(primary) vital signs,' and 'body size and composition.' Regarding to belongingness, 44 out of 52 items (84,6 %) achieved a strong supermajority level and 47 items received supermajority consensus level in the final 3rd Round. Results for easy to understand were somewhat similar, 43 items (82,7 %) gained strong supermajority and 49 items (94,2 %) ended up in supermajority level. As a result, the developed taxonomy is robust.

In total 65 devices were used in JRAs case studies (JRA1=22, JRA2=16, JRA3=26) while number of devices ranged from 1 to 12 between the cases. The utilized devices were mapped with taxonomy subcategories. As a result, 46 out of 52 (88 percent) subcategories were addressed in the case studies, thus indicating widespread opportunities to collect digital biomarker data for hybrid persona creation. The following measurement options were detected: 1) Continuous (e.g. 24h monitoring), Pre/Post, Short time duration (e.g. few minutes), Single event, Frequency, Event/Use/Activity duration (e.g. foot contact time, hours of sleep), Change triggered, Relative (e.g. % share of total), Response time, Cross reference to external data (e.g. weather). Sequenced, Amount (e.g. kg, number of steps) and Choice selection.

3.1.4 Conclusions

Challenges, Barriers & Lessons Learned, Recommendations:

There are widespread opportunities to utilize digital biomarker data for hybrid persona creation. The following opportunities, but not limited to, can be utilized when creating hybrid personas.

Real-time continuous monitoring enables real-time feedback and personalization as well as longitudinal data tracking. However, real-time data collection with high sampling frequency can quickly generate very large dataset, which might lead to high storage costs, information overload and processing speed issues. Therefore, caution should be exercised when collecting real-time data. Pre/Post measurement helps comparing conditions and impact before and after specific events and interventions. Short time duration measurement can be used for capturing brief and critical moments. Single event measurement is suitable for recording specific incidents or occurrences and identifying isolated occurrences with potential consequence.

Frequency analysis helps identifying patterns and trends over time and creates understanding on the regularity of specific behaviours or events. Event/Use/Activity duration provides information on usage patterns and activity engagement as well as gives information on the duration of specific activities or events. Change triggered measurement helps detecting and responding to significant changes in conditions and can be used for triggering alerts based on predefined thresholds. Relative measurement provides understanding on how successful conducted activity was or how results compare for example to desired level. Response time evaluates how much time it takes to react to specific stimuli and can be used for evaluating cognitive processes, decision dynamics, and the efficiency of human performance.

Cross-references to external data enables seeking correlation to external factors which can enhance contextual understanding of the phenomenon. Sequenced data tracking can be used to monitor the progression, evaluate timing and consistency of activities of specific actions. Amount measurement focuses on quantifying and measuring specific quantities and is useful for monitoring changes in amounts over time. Choice selection is recording user preferences or selections and gathers data on decision-making processes.

The list of the above measurement options is suggested to be used as a starting point when creating hybrid-user personas. The mapping of measurement options with the device taxonomy will interlink the outcome measures with measurement type.

3.2 JRA1 Comparative Results and Challenges

It is difficult to make a comparative analysis of the results. Because even though, VITALISE partners decided to focus on stroke patients and patients with mild cognitive impairment where possible in the case studies in some cases the final user participating in the case study were healthy people. Moreover, we tried to align outcome measures, although it was not easy to find common measures available and validated in all languages. Consequently, we concentrated on outcome measures regarding quality of life, patient-reported experience measures for well-being, and user experience.

Comparative Insights Across Case Studies:

1. Effectiveness in Addressing Specific Health Concerns:

- **Short-Arm Human Centrifuge:** Showed potential in improving neuroplasticity and executive functions in stroke patients, indicating its promise for neurological rehabilitation.
- **Art Therapy (GAIA/Spain):** Demonstrated stress relief and emotional well-being among adults and the elderly, highlighting the therapeutic benefits of creative expression.
- **Gradior Cognitive:** Aimed at enhancing cognitive functions in older adults, preliminary feedback suggested improvements in user satisfaction and cognitive training outcomes.

2. Participant Engagement and Experience:

- **Short-Arm Human Centrifuge:** Participants expressed distrust and safety concerns due to the novel use of technology, indicating challenges in participant acceptance and engagement.
- **Art Therapy:** Encountered scepticism about effectiveness but ultimately was seen as enriching, especially when creating a supportive and non-judgmental environment.
- **Gradior Cognitive:** Faced challenges in recruiting participants but showed promising user experience and satisfaction once individuals engaged with the cognitive training program.

3. Technological and Logistical Challenges:

- **Short-Arm Human Centrifuge:** Faced high maintenance costs and strict exclusion criteria, limiting wider applicability and scalability.
- **Art Therapy:** Had to address logistical issues like venue accessibility and material provision, emphasizing the need for operational flexibility.
- **Gradior Cognitive:** Experienced challenges in recruitment and technical issues, highlighting the importance of robust support systems and clear communication channels.

4. Methodological and Ethical Considerations:

- All case studies grappled with ethical considerations around safety, privacy, and informed consent, underscoring the importance of adhering to ethical guidelines in health-related research.
- The need for clear and effective communication with participants about the research process and interventions was a common theme, particularly in overcoming initial scepticism or resistance.

3.2.1 Summary of Comparative Insights:

While each case study targeted different aspects of health and wellbeing, from physical and neurological rehabilitation to mental health and emotional well-being, several cross-cutting themes emerge. These include the critical importance of participant engagement and experience, the challenges posed by technological and logistical implementation, and the overarching need for ethical research practices. Comparative effectiveness, in terms of specific health outcomes, would require a deeper quantitative analysis, ideally involving direct metrics of improvement (e.g., scales for measuring cognitive function, mood improvement, etc.) and participant feedback across the different interventions.

General challenges across case studies:

- **Technical and Ethical Concerns:** Each case study faced technical challenges specific to the intervention and ethical considerations, particularly concerning patient safety and data privacy.

- **Engagement and Accessibility:** Engaging participants and ensuring interventions are accessible and acceptable to various user groups were common challenges.
- **Logistical Issues:** Organizing sessions, managing equipment, and adapting to participants' needs required significant logistical planning.
- **Evaluation of Effectiveness:** Measuring the effectiveness of interventions and the impact on participants' health and wellbeing involved complex methodologies and highlighted the need for comprehensive evaluation frameworks.

3.3 Economic impact assessment

In the landscape of healthcare innovation, the integration of technology holds immense promise for enhancing rehabilitation practices and fostering advancements in health and well-being. Recognizing the transformative potential of innovative technologies in rehabilitation, the VITALISE initiative emerges as pioneer of collaborative research aimed at harmonizing living lab procedures and open infrastructures across Europe and beyond. With a primary focus on the health and well-being domain, VITALISE seeks to streamline research activities and promote the adoption of cutting-edge technologies to bolster rehabilitation efforts.

The Joint Research Activities (JRAs) presented in the current document offer a glimpse into the multifaceted nature of healthcare research, spanning diverse domains such as stroke rehabilitation, stress management, cognitive therapy, and gait training. Each case study represents a concerted effort to explore the efficacy, usability, and potential ramifications of novel interventions within the healthcare landscape.

In the ever-changing world of healthcare, where the needs of people are growing and technology is advancing, it is crucial to study how healthcare interventions affect people's lives beyond just the medical aspect. By examining the social and economic effects of these case studies, the aim is to comprehend how they affect aspects which consider the people who work in healthcare domain, the challenges faced by caregivers, the development of new technologies, and the overall impact within society.

3.3.1 Short Arm Human Centrifuge (SAHC)

The **Short Arm Human Centrifuge (SAHC)** represents a cutting-edge innovation in the domain of stroke rehabilitation and neuroplasticity research. By offering a unique approach to enhancing rehabilitation outcomes, the SAHC holds the potential to not only transform patient care but also generate significant economic impacts across various sectors. Focusing on the multiple economic implications of the SAHC in the context of stroke rehabilitation and neuroplasticity research, stroke often results in enduring disabilities, necessitating extensive medical care and rehabilitation. The innovative capabilities of the SAHC offer potential optimizations in rehabilitation outcomes, potentially curtailing the need for prolonged hospital stays and ongoing therapy sessions. This has the ripple effect of **cost savings for healthcare systems, insurers, and patients** alike, mitigating the economic burden associated with stroke-related disabilities and fostering improved resource allocation within the healthcare sector.

Moreover, stroke survivors frequently encounter obstacles when re-entering the workforce due to physical and cognitive impairments. By facilitating more effective rehabilitation and enhancing functional outcomes, the SAHC can support greater **workforce participation** among stroke survivors. This not only bolsters individual economic stability but also diminishes dependence on social welfare programs, ultimately contributing to broader economic productivity and societal well-being. This increased workforce participation not only enhances individual economic stability but also contributes to overall economic productivity, reducing reliance on social welfare programs.

Furthermore, the development and utilization of advanced medical technologies like the SAHC have the potential to **create employment opportunities** across diverse fields, including engineering,

healthcare, and research. Additionally, the demand for skilled professionals to operate and administer rehabilitation programs incorporating the SAHC could catalyze job creation within allied health sectors, fostering workforce expansion and professional growth.

Finally, while challenging to quantify economically, the **improved quality of life** for stroke survivors and their families stemming from enhanced rehabilitation outcomes with the SAHC is invaluable. Improved mobility and independence not only reduce caregiving demands but also promote social engagement and overall well-being. These benefits can lead to decreased healthcare and social support expenses in the long term, underscoring the broader societal and economic value of the SAHC in enhancing quality of life.

In conclusion, the economic ramifications of the SAHC in stroke rehabilitation and neuroplasticity research extends beyond direct healthcare cost savings, encompassing job creation and advancements in quality of life. These collective impacts contribute significantly to societal welfare and economic prosperity, highlighting the multifaceted benefits of integrating the SAHC into healthcare practices.

3.3.2 Art Therapy

Art therapy delivered through podcasts for stress relief among adults holds significant socioeconomic implications. Firstly, effective stress management through art therapy can lead to **decreased healthcare costs** associated with treating stress-related physical and mental health conditions. By reducing the need for medical interventions and therapy sessions, this decline in healthcare utilization can alleviate financial strains on healthcare systems and insurance providers.

Moreover, offering accessible stress relief interventions like art therapy podcasts can enhance individuals' mental **well-being and productivity** across personal and professional domains. This can result in reduced absenteeism and presenteeism due to stress-related issues, ultimately bolstering workplace productivity and economic performance.

Successful stress relief through art therapy can contribute to an overall improvement in individuals' **quality of life**, fostering better social functioning, improved relationships, and heightened emotional well-being. These positive outcomes promote societal cohesion and elevate happiness indices.

Additionally, the development and dissemination of art therapy podcasts may generate employment opportunities for artists, therapists, content creators, and podcast producers. This can stimulate **job creation** and economic growth within the creative industries and digital media sectors.

Podcasts serve as a convenient and **inclusive** platform for delivering art therapy interventions to a diverse audience, including individuals with physical disabilities, limited mobility, or geographical constraints. This heightened accessibility promotes inclusivity and ensures that individuals from various socioeconomic backgrounds can access stress relief interventions.

In summary, art therapy podcasts offer accessible stress relief solutions with wide-ranging socioeconomic benefits, such as healthcare cost reduction, workforce productivity and employment opportunities.

3.3.3 Gradior Cognitive

Gradior Cognitive, a digital tool designed for cognitive training and stress relief in older adults, has garnered attention for its potential socioeconomic impact. By enhancing cognitive function and reducing stress levels in older individuals, Gradior Cognitive may not only improve individual well-being but also contribute to broader economic and societal outcomes.

Specifically, its successful implementation can **reduce healthcare costs** associated with cognitive decline and mental health issues, thereby decreasing expenditures related to hospitalizations and

medications. Moreover, improving cognitive function and reducing stress among older adults can **enhance their productivity in the workforce** or volunteer activities, potentially leading to economic growth and reduced reliance on caregiving services for retirees.

The development of digital health technologies like Gradior Cognitive may create **job opportunities** in sectors such as software development and healthcare IT, stimulating employment and economic growth. Additionally, it can contribute to overall **quality of life** improvements, fostering greater social engagement and independence among older adults.

Furthermore, **research and development** efforts focused on Gradior Cognitive contribute to technological innovation in healthcare, attracting investment and driving economic growth in the digital health industry. These interventions also promote **health equity** by reaching underserved populations and addressing disparities in healthcare access and outcomes.

By promoting cognitive health and stress relief, Gradior Cognitive may delay cognitive decline onset, **reducing the need for long-term care services**. This leads to significant cost savings for individuals, families, and governments. Gradior Cognitive's intervention preserves cognitive function, lessening the risk of conditions like dementia. This delay in decline reduces individuals' reliance on costly long-term care, alleviating financial strain. Consequently, families can maintain independence and governments can allocate healthcare resources more efficiently, benefiting society as a whole.

Overall, investing in interventions like Gradior Cognitive promises significant societal and economic benefits, reducing reliance on long-term care services and healthcare expenditures while enhancing productivity and individual well-being.

3.3.4 Virtual Mirror Therapy

Virtual mirror therapy, a cutting-edge approach in stroke rehabilitation, has sparked interest due to its potential socioeconomic impact. By leveraging technology to enhance rehabilitation outcomes for stroke patients, virtual mirror therapy not only improves individual well-being but also holds promise for broader economic and societal implications. Virtual mirror therapy's introduction as a rehabilitation method holds the potential for **cost-saving benefits** within healthcare systems. By replacing traditional mirror therapy setups with virtual alternatives, the therapy becomes more accessible and cost-effective, reducing equipment expenses and streamlining therapy delivery processes. This streamlined approach can lead to decreased healthcare expenditures associated with stroke rehabilitation, benefiting both patients and healthcare providers.

Furthermore, the efficiency gains achieved through virtual mirror therapy can enhance **workforce productivity** among healthcare professionals. With a user-friendly and effective therapeutic tool at their disposal, clinicians can optimize their time spent with patients, potentially increasing patient throughput or reallocating resources to other critical areas of care delivery. This optimization not only improves patient outcomes but also contributes to overall healthcare system efficiency.

The study's focus on virtual mirror therapy contributes to **technological innovation** in the healthcare sector. By advancing digital therapeutic solutions like virtual reality applications for stroke rehabilitation, the research fosters innovation and entrepreneurship. This innovation attracts investment and drives economic growth in the digital health industry, creating opportunities for technological advancements and economic prosperity.

Moreover, the development and implementation of virtual mirror therapy solutions can stimulate **job creation** across various sectors. Opportunities may arise in software development, healthcare IT, and digital health consulting as demand increases for trained professionals to administer and support these technologies. This job creation not only increases economic growth but also fosters workforce development and expansion in healthcare and related industries.

Enhancing stroke rehabilitation with virtual mirror therapy can lead to improved patient satisfaction and engagement in therapy sessions. The immersive and interactive nature of virtual mirror therapy may motivate patients to adhere to their rehabilitation regimens, resulting in better treatment outcomes and potentially **reducing the need for long-term care services**. Ultimately, this patient-centered approach improves overall patient experience and contributes to better health outcomes.

Moreover, virtual mirror therapy has the potential to address disparities in access to stroke rehabilitation services. By leveraging digital technology, virtual mirror therapy can overcome geographical barriers and provide equitable access to innovative rehabilitation interventions. This enhanced accessibility promotes **health equity** and contributes to overall societal well-being by ensuring that all individuals have access to effective rehabilitation services, regardless of their location or socioeconomic status.

In summary, the socioeconomic impacts of assessing virtual mirror therapy for stroke patients encompass a wide range of benefits, including cost reductions in healthcare, increased workforce productivity, technological innovation, job creation, improved patient experience, and enhanced accessibility to rehabilitation services. These collective impacts not only advance stroke rehabilitation practices but also contribute to fostering societal well-being and equitable healthcare access.

3.3.5 Teledance

The Teledance intervention for stroke rehabilitation represents a promising approach with the potential to yield substantial socioeconomic benefits. By harnessing technology to provide dance-based rehabilitation remotely, Teledance offers opportunities to enhance healthcare access, improve rehabilitation outcomes, promote workforce participation, support caregivers, and drive technological innovation in healthcare delivery. In this analysis the focus is on the socioeconomic implications of Teledance highlighting its capacity to instigate positive transformations across multiple dimensions of healthcare and societal well-being.

More specifically, if proven effective, Teledance could enhance functional outcomes and the overall **quality of life** for stroke survivors. This improvement may translate into **reduced long-term healthcare costs** associated with stroke care and rehabilitation, thereby easing the burden on healthcare systems and potentially reallocating resources for other critical needs.

Moreover, by improving rehabilitation outcomes and functional abilities, Teledance may facilitate the **reintegration of stroke survivors into the workforce**. This could lead to heightened productivity and economic contributions from those who are able to return to work, while also reducing dependency on social welfare programs, benefiting both individuals and the economy at large.

Furthermore, the remote delivery of Teledance interventions has the potential to **broaden access to rehabilitation services** for stroke survivors facing barriers to in-person care. This expanded access can address disparities in healthcare access and outcomes among different socioeconomic groups, promoting equity in healthcare delivery.

The development and implementation of Teledance interventions signify advancements in technology-enabled healthcare delivery. This progress can catalyze further innovation in telehealth and digital health solutions, benefiting not only stroke rehabilitation but also various other aspects of healthcare. In summary, the socioeconomic impact of Teledance for stroke rehabilitation could encompass improvements in healthcare access, rehabilitation outcomes, workforce participation, caregiver support, and technological innovation in healthcare delivery.

3.3.6 Augmented Gait Training

The WALKAGAIN pilot study, with its focus on augmented gait training for stroke rehabilitation, represents a pioneering initiative with multifaceted socioeconomic implications. At its core, the

potential benefits of this study extend beyond the individual level, encompassing broader societal and economic dimensions.

One significant socioeconomic impact of the WALKAGAIN pilot study lies in the realm of **healthcare cost reduction**. By improving walking abilities among stroke survivors, augmented gait training has the potential to mitigate the need for extensive ongoing medical care and support services. This reduction in healthcare utilization could translate into substantial cost savings for healthcare systems, insurers, and individual patients, thereby optimizing resource allocation within the healthcare sector.

Moreover, the enhanced mobility resulting from augmented gait training holds promise for facilitating the reintegration of stroke survivors into the workforce. As individuals regain independence in mobility, they may be better positioned to return to their previous occupations or seek new employment opportunities. This **increased workforce participation** not only benefits stroke survivors by fostering economic self-sufficiency but also contributes to broader economic productivity and stability.

Additionally, the potential alleviation of **caregiver burden** represents another significant socioeconomic impact of the WALKAGAIN pilot study. Caregivers, often family members or loved ones, play a crucial role in supporting stroke survivors with various daily activities, including mobility-related tasks. By enhancing the walking abilities of stroke survivors, augmented gait training may reduce the physical and emotional strain experienced by caregivers, enabling them to allocate their time and resources more effectively. This, in turn, can enhance their ability to participate in the workforce or pursue other personal and professional endeavors, ultimately contributing to economic productivity and well-being.

Furthermore, the integration of advanced technologies such as biomechanical devices, haptic feedback systems, and virtual reality environments into augmented gait training represents a notable avenue for **technological innovation in healthcare**. Successful implementation of these technologies not only enhances the effectiveness of rehabilitation interventions but also fosters further research and development in the field of rehabilitation technology. This innovation not only benefits stroke survivors but also holds potential applications for individuals with other mobility impairments, thereby addressing broader healthcare needs and promoting technological advancement.

Moreover, the collaborative nature of the WALKAGAIN pilot study, with its establishment of an international common dataset and the conceptualization of standardized training protocols, fosters collaboration among researchers and clinicians worldwide. This collaborative approach facilitates the sharing of knowledge, expertise, and best practices in stroke rehabilitation, ultimately enhancing the quality and consistency of care delivery across diverse healthcare settings. By **promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange**, the WALKAGAIN pilot study contributes to the advancement of evidence-based practices and the standardization of care, benefiting a larger population of stroke survivors and enhancing overall healthcare outcomes.

In brief, the socioeconomic impact of the WALKAGAIN pilot study on augmented gait training is multifaceted and far-reaching. Through its potential to reduce healthcare costs, promote workforce participation, alleviate caregiver burden, foster technological innovation, and enhance collaboration in stroke rehabilitation research and practice, the study holds promise for improving healthcare delivery and enhancing overall societal well-being.

3.3.7 Aggregated Use Cases Results

Innovative rehabilitation technologies have the potential to not only advance patient care and outcomes but also to have significant economic impacts within the healthcare system. By incorporating cutting-edge technologies into rehabilitation programs, such as virtual reality, robotics, and AI-driven interventions, healthcare providers can **improve treatment efficiency, shorten recovery times, and enhance patient engagement**. These advancements can lead to cost savings

by reducing the need for extensive in-patient care, minimizing hospital readmissions, and potentially lowering overall healthcare expenditures.

Moreover, the implementation of innovative rehabilitation technologies can result in long-term economic benefits by improving patient outcomes and quality of life. By utilizing these technologies to tailor rehabilitation programs to individual needs and monitor progress more effectively, healthcare providers can achieve better results with fewer resources. This personalized approach can lead to **reduced healthcare costs** associated with prolonged treatments, unnecessary procedures, and preventable complications.

Additionally, the adoption of innovative rehabilitation technologies may stimulate economic growth through research and development investments, job creation in the healthcare technology sector, and the establishment of new treatment paradigms. As these technologies become more integrated into mainstream healthcare practices, there may be opportunities for cost-effective scalability, increased accessibility to advanced rehabilitation services, and potential revenue generation through licensing or commercialization of successful innovations.

Overall, the economic impact of innovative rehabilitation technologies is multifaceted, with the potential to drive efficiency, improve outcomes, and create new opportunities for economic growth within the healthcare industry. By embracing and leveraging these advancements, healthcare systems can not only enhance patient care but also optimize resource utilization and foster innovation in the field of rehabilitation.

4 Recommendations for Rehabilitation

The JRAs described in the current report demonstrated co-creation activities and implemented a variety of small-scale study designs which illustrate Living Lab practices and infrastructure.

Research activities during the co-creation phase provided insights into different stakeholders' views (i.e., end users, clinicians, caregivers) on the role of technology in rehabilitation on a European level (and beyond) as well as specific suggestions regarding rehabilitation innovations.

Phase 2 (small-scale pilots) provided insights into end user experiences and usability of six selected neuropsychological and/or physical rehabilitation interventions for healthy people and stroke patients and individuals with mild cognitive impairment.

During the bi-weekly WP5 meetings and common JRA stand-up meetings consortium partners agreed on harmonised screening, outcomes and outcome measures for Living Lab research in the context of technology in rehabilitation.

Together, these research activities provided an opportunity for all involved Living Labs (and beyond) to gain knowledge on specific technologies intended for rehabilitation and to discuss and adopt each other's technologies and/or procedures in order to harmonise Living Lab procedures and infrastructures concerning the use of innovative technology in rehabilitation on a European level.

Comparability and Application Challenges: Address how to effectively compare and apply findings from different monitoring resolutions and settings.

Gait Analysis and Patient Management Tools: Include insights on gait patterns, stability, strength, and the use of patient management tools.

Based on insights gathered from the VITALISE project's case studies we summarise some recommendations focused on rehabilitation in both clinical and home settings, addressing comparability and application challenges, as well as insights into gait analysis and patient users management tools:

Clinical and Home Setting Insights

Integration of Technology: Utilize wearable devices and digital platforms for continuous monitoring in both settings, ensuring technologies are user-friendly and non-intrusive. In clinical settings, advanced equipment can be used for detailed assessments, whereas home settings should leverage simpler, more intuitive technology.

Personalization of Rehabilitation Programs: Tailor rehabilitation exercises and interventions to individual patient needs and capabilities, considering the differences in the clinical and home environments. Personalization enhances adherence and maximizes recovery outcomes.

Education and Support: Provide patients and caregivers with education and training on using rehabilitation technologies and performing exercises correctly at home. Regular virtual check-ins by clinicians can support this process.

Comparability and Application Challenges

Standardization of Data Collection: Implement standardized protocols for data collection across different settings to ensure comparability. This includes the use of common metrics and validated assessment tools for evaluating patient progress.

Interoperability of Systems: Ensure that patient management tools and databases used in both clinical and home settings are interoperable, allowing for seamless data sharing and analysis. This facilitates a holistic view of patient progress over time.

Adaptive Algorithms: Develop and utilize adaptive algorithms that can interpret data from varying resolutions and settings, providing personalized feedback and recommendations for adjustments in the rehabilitation plan.

Gait Analysis and Patient Management Tools

Utilization of Wearable Sensors: Employ wearable sensors for real-time gait analysis to assess patterns, stability, and strength. These sensors can provide valuable insights into the patient's progress and the effectiveness of rehabilitation interventions.

Integration with Patient Management Platforms: Incorporate gait analysis data into comprehensive patient management platforms that track a wide range of health metrics. This allows clinicians to adjust rehabilitation plans based on objective data.

Feedback Mechanisms: Implement feedback mechanisms that provide patients with real-time insights into their gait patterns and suggest corrections. This can enhance the effectiveness of gait training exercises, especially in home settings where professional supervision is limited.

Predictive Analytics: Leverage predictive analytics to identify potential risks or areas of concern based on gait analysis and other health metrics. This proactive approach can help in adjusting rehabilitation interventions before issues become more serious.

Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration: Foster collaboration between engineers, clinicians, and data scientists to develop and refine tools for gait analysis and patient management. This multidisciplinary approach ensures that tools are clinically relevant, technologically advanced, and user-centered.

Overall Recommendations

Continuity of Care: Ensure that rehabilitation efforts in clinical and home settings are complementary, forming a continuum of care that supports the patient's journey towards recovery.

Patient/users Empowerment: Empower patients by involving them in the decision-making process, setting realistic goals, and providing tools and knowledge for self-management.

Efficacy and Safety Monitoring: Continuously monitor the efficacy and safety of rehabilitation interventions, adjusting as necessary to optimize outcomes and minimize risks.

5 Conclusion

The exploration of rehabilitation strategies across clinical and home settings, as well as the utilization of gait analysis and patient management tools, underscores a significant evolution in how rehabilitation services are delivered and monitored.

The integration of technology into rehabilitation processes presents a promising avenue for enhancing patient outcomes, facilitating personalized care, and ensuring continuity between clinical and home-based rehabilitation.

Key findings from the Vitalise JRA case studies include the importance of personalized rehabilitation programs, the potential of wearable technologies for continuous monitoring, and the critical role of data standardization for comparability across settings.

Key Findings:

- **Personalized Rehabilitation:** Tailoring rehabilitation to individual needs and capabilities is paramount, highlighting the need for adaptable and user-friendly technologies that can be employed both in clinical settings and at home.
- **Technology Integration:** Wearable sensors and digital platforms have emerged as crucial tools for real-time monitoring and feedback, offering insights into patient progress and facilitating remote supervision by healthcare professionals.
- **Data Standardization and Interoperability:** Establishing standardized protocols for data collection and ensuring interoperability between different patient management systems are essential for the effective comparison and application of rehabilitation findings.

Future Directions:

- **Advanced Analytical Tools:** Future research should focus on developing sophisticated algorithms and analytical tools capable of interpreting complex data from diverse monitoring technologies. This includes predictive analytics for identifying risks and customizing rehabilitation interventions proactively.
- **Holistic Health Monitoring:** Expanding the scope of monitoring to include a wider range of physical and mental health parameters could provide a more comprehensive understanding of patient well-being and rehabilitation needs.
- **Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration:** Strengthening collaboration across disciplines can drive innovation in rehabilitation technologies and methodologies. This includes partnerships between clinicians, engineers, data scientists, and patients themselves.
- **Regulatory Frameworks and Ethical Considerations:** Developing clear regulatory frameworks and ethical guidelines for the use of technology in rehabilitation is crucial to ensure patient privacy, data security, and equitable access to innovative treatments.
- **Long-term Effectiveness Studies:** There is a need for longitudinal studies to assess the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of technology-integrated rehabilitation programs, especially in home settings where patient adherence and engagement can vary.
- **Integration of Mental Health Interventions:** Considering the psychological aspects of rehabilitation, future initiatives should explore the integration of mental health interventions into comprehensive rehabilitation programs to support overall patient well-being.

In conclusion, the integration of innovative technologies and personalized approaches in rehabilitation presents a transformative potential for enhancing patient outcomes. The continuous evolution of patient management tools and monitoring technologies, coupled with a focus on holistic and personalized care, paves the way for a future where rehabilitation services are more accessible, effective, and aligned with the individual needs of patients. As the field progresses, it is imperative to

D5.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA1

address the challenges related to technology adoption, data management, and cross-disciplinary collaboration to fully realize the benefits of these advancements in rehabilitation science.

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7 Annexes

7.1 Additional pictures of the co-creation sessions

7.1.1 Virtual mirror therapy co-creation session (LiCalab/Belgium)

7.2 Additional pictures of the small-scale pilot studies

7.2.1 Art therapy (GAIA/Spain)

7.2.2 Virtual (mirror) therapy in rehabilitation (LiCalab/Belgium)